

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D6.2. Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems

Date of delivery – 31/12/2024

Authors: Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Mathieu Lepot (INSA); Juan Naves, José Anta, Alejandra Pimiento (UDC); Antonio Moreno Ródenas (Deltares); Alma Schellart, James Shucksmith (USFD)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101008626

DOCUMENT TRACKS DETAILS

Project acronym	Co-UDlabs
Project title	Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs communities
Starting date	01.05.2021
Duration	48 months
Call identifier	H2020-INFRAIA-2020-1
Grant Agreement No	101008626

Deliverable Information	
Deliverable number	D6.2
Work package number	6
Deliverable title	Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems
Lead beneficiary	EAWAG
Author(s)	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Mathieu Lepot (INSA); Juan Naves, José Anta, Alejandra Pimiento (UDC); Antonio Moreno Ródenas (Deltares); Alma Schellart, James Shucksmith (USFD)
Due date	31/12/2024
Actual submission date	31/12/2024
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

VERSION MANAGEMENT

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
VO.1	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski, Mathieu Lepot (INSA); Juan Naves, José Anta, Maria Pimiento (UDC); Antonio Rodenas (Deltares); Alma Schellart, James Schucksmith (UoS)	02/12/2024	First draft

D6.2. Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems

V0.2	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra (UDC); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA)	16/12/2024	Draft ready for lay-out
V0.3	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jose Anta, Andrea Ciambra (UDC); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA)	20/12/2024	Appendices consolidation and lay- out
V 1.0	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA); Andrea Ciambra, José Anta (UDC)	20/12/2024	Final draft
V 1.1	Pierre Lechevallier, Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG); Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA); Andrea Ciambra, José Anta (UDC)	27/12/2024	Final draft consolidation, ready for submission
V 2.0	Jean-Luc Bertrand-Krajewski (INSA)	04/04/2025	Correction of typos in sections 3.2 and Appendix B. Completion of section 3.8.
V 2.1	Juan Naves (UDC) ; Jörg Rieckermann (EAWAG)	17/04/2025	Including flow estimation analysis for DischargeKeeper camera, Completion of section 3.6., Update Appendix A, Appendix C.

All information in this document only reflects the author's view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

List of figures	6
List of tables.....	9
Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project.....	10
List of acronyms.....	11
Executive summary.....	13
1. Introduction.....	14
2. Methods: unified approach for sensor testing.....	15
2.1. Sensor selection	15
2.2. Testing plan	15
2.3. Data validation	16
2.4. Sensor evaluation.....	17
3. Results and discussion.....	18
3.1. Sensor 1: Proteus.....	18
3.2. Sensor 2: PAH 22.....	
3.3. Sensor 3: LPICM.....	27
3.4. Sensor 4: ISA 31.....	
3.5. Sensor 5: MV.X.....	35
3.6. Sensor 6: DischargeKeeper.....	39
3.7. Sensor 7: Pipe mapping FSB.....	44
3.8. Sensor 8: Lidar sediment mapping.....	51
3.9. Summary of the results and discussion.....	57
4. Data validation with UDMT	59
5. Data availability	65
6. Contributions to the objectives of the Co-UDlabs project	65
6.1. Objective 1: Fostering cooperation and innovation in Urban Drainage.....	66
6.2. Objective 2: Facilitating Transnational Access to Research Facilities.....	66
6.3. Objective 3: Strengthening services of RIs at the European level through Joint Research Activities	66
7. Conclusions.....	68
References.....	69
Appendix A: sensor testing sheets for each sensor.....	72

Appendix B: Detailed report on the PAH sensor testing	82
Appendix C: Assessment of DischargeKeeper Flow Monitoring Quality	95

List of figures

Figure 1: E.coli concentration measured by the calibrated sensor and in laboratory, and rainfall for the events E0-E5.....	20
Figure 2: Calibration result plot for event E1 (provided by RS instrument).....	21
Figure 3: Validation result plot for events E2-E4.....	22
Figure 4: Trios EnviroFlu-HC 500 probe (source: Trios company website).	23
Figure 5: Left: scheme of the shelter equipment (source: INSA); right: monitoring flume with sensors in the shelter (source: Nicolas Walcker).....	23
Figure 6: Left and middle: the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor at the end of testing in the Chassieu monitoring flume; right: accidental spill of hydrocarbons at the outlet of the Chassieu catchment (sources: Nicolas Walcker).	24
Figure 7: Plot of Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor concentrations vs. Carso laboratory PAHs concentrations, with regression line for total sample concentrations.....	25
Figure 8: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 30 May to 31 Dec. 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: outlet discharge, b: turbidity, c: PAH concentration.	26
Figure 9: Impressions of different sensor tests in the lab (top left), pilot reactors (top right) and full-scale sewer systems of Lenzburg (bottom left). Sensor head gets after immersion in wastewater (bottom right)....	28
Figure 10: EC-ammonium models in Eawag (a), Lenzburg treatment plant (b) and Lenzburg sewers (c). The relationship during wet weather is shown in red.	29
Figure 11: Comparison of the ISE ammonium and LPCIM conductivity for the Lenzburg data between 04/03/2020 and 06/03/2020, showing a time shift between peaks of EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ during dry weather.	30
Figure 12: (a) Installation of the ISA sensor in a flume at Eawag. (b): UDC installation of the ISA and other probes in a flume.....	32
Figure 13: Scatter plot for actual vs predicted $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentration (a) at Eawag, (b) at UDC.	33
Figure 14: Comparison of the laboratory measurements and the dry weather calibration during the 13/08/2023 week for the Eawag dataset, showing that the model follows the expected trend.....	33
Figure 15: Comparison of the performance of the dry and wet weather calibrations for a rain event, showing that the wet weather calibration performs best after the rain.....	34
Figure 16: (left) Picture of the flume used for the Eawag tests of the MV.X hyperspectral camera; (right) Drawing of the camera installation.	35
Figure 17: (left) Picture of the Monash setup for hyperspectral data acquisition; (right) Drawing of the camera installation.....	36
Figure 18: Evaluation of the flume turbidity model (a) and of the Monash turbidity model (b). Both models have similar performances with a RMSE around 13 NTU.....	37
Figure 19: Evaluation of the flume turbidity model (test set). Model performances are only slightly lower than on the training set, with an increase of RMSE of 1.1 NTU, showing the robustness of the model.....	37
Figure 20: Preliminary results for the modelling of ammonium (publication in preparation). Model performances are not as good as UV-vis sensor, but ammonium trend can be detected.....	38

Figure 21: Installation of the DischargeKeeper in the trunk sewer at the Eawag hall. 41

Figure 22: (left) BENS flume and scheme of the sensors installed in the facility; (right) Processing of a 5-second-long video, the red line shows the optically measured water level and the arrows are the velocity vectors, the lighter colour indicates faster velocities. 41

Figure 23: Surface velocity time series DischargeKeeper (red) and NIVUS (green). 42

Figure 24: Depth (left) and velocity (right) results obtained from DischargeKeeper, UB-Flow velocity profiler and ultrasound depth sensors for experiment ST25, where flow varies for a certain slope and downstream boundary condition. 43

Figure 25: Scatterplot of credible NIVUS data vs. DischargeKeeper CFD-based flow estimates shows that the DK underestimates the flow data in comparison to the operational flow meter, but deviations are <10% in medium and high flows (see Appendix C). 43

Figure 26: A)/B) IMU prototype during the in-pipe testing, C) IMU prototype, D) Control server and user interface 46

Figure 27: Example of data extract from Test P1.2. A) Measurements from IMU (accel, mag, gyro), B) Lidar data, C) Post-processed Euler angles (reconstructed orientation), D) Synchronization of sensors, E) Estimates of velocity and position at the end of the pipe section. 50

Figure 28: Examples of camera top-view from the pipe tests (5 Mpix, 5 fps). 50

Figure 29: DJI Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor (source: www.gim-international.com) 52

Figure 30: Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor installed on a drone for testing (photo: R. Poncet, INSA Lyon). 52

Figure 31: Django Reinhardt stormwater infiltration tank in Chassieu, Lyon, France (boundaries of the infiltration tank in yellow). (source: JLBK from Google Maps). 53

Figure 32: Vegetation in Django Reinhardt stormwater infiltration tank. Top: in 2015 (source: OTHU; bottom: in May 2023 during the Lidar testing (source: INSA). The growth of the vegetation is noticeable, with many bushes and small trees. 53

Figure 33: Examples of solids laid on the bottom of the infiltration tank for the Lidar sensor testing. 54

Figure 34: View of flight #1 Lidar data (figure made with the Matlab Lidar toolbox 24.2). 55

Figure 35: View of flight #2 Lidar data (figure made with the Matlab Lidar toolbox 24.2). 55

Figure 36: Lidar images cutting structure. 56

Figure 37: Lidar image of the difference flight #2 – flight #1. 56

Figure 40: Extract of the PAHDV.csv file. 60

Figure 41: PAHTR.csv file. 61

Figure 42: PAHRM.csv file. 61

Figure 43: PAHUM.csv file. 61

Figure 44: Screenshot of the UDMT just before launching the selected data validation tests. 62

Figure 45: UDMT physical range test outcomes. 62

Figure 46: UDMT sensor measuring range test outcomes. 63

Figure 47: UDMT expert range test outcomes. 63

Figure 48: UDMT gradient test outcomes.	64
Figure 49: UDMT relative uncertainty test outcomes.	64
Figure 50: UDMT global validation based on the median grade of all applied tests.	65
Figure B51: Trios EnviroFlu-HC 500 probe (source: Trios company website).	82
Figure B52: Left: aerial view of the Chassieu catchment (source: JLBK); right: monitoring shelter at catchment outlet (source: OTHU).	83
Figure B53: Left: scheme of the shelter equipment (source: JLBK); right: monitoring flume with sensors in the shelter (source: Nicolas Walcker).	83
Figure B54: Left: the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor at the end of testing in the Chassieu monitoring flume source: Nicolas Walcker); right: accidental spill of hydrocarbons at the outlet of the Chassieu catchment (source: Nicolas Walcker).	84
Figure B55: Boxplots of the 240 concentrations measured with the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor for each sample (among the $9 \times 240 = 2160$ values, six were negative and have been replaced by NaN). Light blue columns indicate the three samples with analyses of dissolved fraction.	87
Figure B56: Bar plot of CARSO laboratory measurements of PAHs concentrations. Only the 18 among 30 analysed PAHs that have been quantified (i.e. concentrations > LoQ) in at least one sample are displayed.	87
Figure B57: Plot of Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor concentrations vs. CARSO laboratory PAHs concentrations, with regression line for total sample concentrations.	88
Figure B58: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 30 May to 31 December 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: rainfall intensity, b: feeding pump, c: outlet discharge, d: conductivity, e: turbidity, f: PAH concentration.	89
Figure B59: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 14 to 30 Nov 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: rainfall intensity, b: outlet discharge, c: turbidity, d: PAH concentration.	90
Figure B60: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume on 28-30 Nov 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: rainfall intensity, b: outlet discharge, c: turbidity, d: PAH concentration, e: zoom on PAH concentration under $80 \mu\text{g/L}$	91
Figure B61: PAH sensor concentration vs. turbidity on 28-30 November 2022.	92
Figure B62: PAH sensor concentration vs. outlet discharge from 30 May to 31 December 2022.	92
Figure B63: PAH sensor concentration vs. turbidity from 30 May to 31 December 2022.	93
Figure B64: Flow data at experimental Hall of Eawag. NIVUS OCM-Pro, 2019-04-01 until 2019-05-31. Yellow range labels data used in comparison (2019-04-16), Grey Area depicts typical dry weather conditions used for Scattergraph reference.	96
Figure B65: Left: typical dry weather conditions used for scattergraph analysis, Right: Scattergraph resulted in regular flow behaviour with an estimated roughness of $n=0.0174$	98
Figure B66: Top, left: Scattergraph of the Nivus data, right: Credible data within $\pm 20\%$ of the Manning-relationship. Bottom: Left: Discharge keeper compared to credible NIVUS data (1min aggregation), Discharge keeper compared to credible NIVUS data (5min aggregation)	99
Figure B67: Scatterplot of credible NIVUS vs. DK data shows that the DK underestimates the flow data, but deviations are not large in medium and high flows.	100

Figure B68: Comparison of DischargeKeeper and Nivus flow measurements for April 16, 2019. Top: Time series of 1-minute averaged flow rates from the DischargeKeeper and the credible Nivus meter, filtered with a low-pass parameter $n=0.0174$, Bottom Left: Boxplot of residual flow (DischargeKeeper minus Nivus) stratified by Nivus flow clusters (Low, Medium, High), showing a decrease in bias and variability with increasing flow, Bottom Right: Residuals over time, color-coded by flow cluster, highlighting larger discrepancies during low-flow conditions and improved agreement at higher flows. 101

List of tables

Table 1: Overview of the 8 tested sensors and of the testing institutions for test phases 1 and 2.....	15
Table 2: Quantitative indicators used for the evaluation of the operational performances of the tested technologies (1: poor, 5: excellent).....	18
Table 3: E. coli sampling event dates, durations and sampling frequencies. Rainfall duration is based on analysis of radar rainfall data from the UK MET office.....	19
Table 4: List of the 30 PAH molecules measured by Carso laboratory, with the corresponding Limit of Quantification (LoQ).....	24
Table 5: Components of IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) sensor prototype.	45
Table 6: Experimental matrix of tests done with the FSB pipe mapping sensor.....	46
Table 7: Summary of static IMU stability and restart mean and zero-drift tests.....	48
Table 8: Solids laid on the bottom of the infiltration tank for the Lidar sensor testing.....	54
Table 9: Summary of the sensor evaluations (DK= Discharge Keeper, PM = Pipe Mapping, SM=Sediment Mapping).	58
Table 10: Link to the repositories where data are openly available.	65
Table B11: List of the 30 PAH molecules measured by Carso laboratory in total sample (T) and dissolved fraction (D) of the collected samples.	85
Table B12: List of collected samples with the analysed fraction (total sample or dissolved fraction).	85
Table B13: Results of measurements on the 9 samples.....	86
Table B5: Summary of DischargeKeeper performance across Nivus-defined flow categories. The accuracy improves with increasing flow, as shown by decreasing bias and RMSE values from low to high flow conditions.	100

Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
EC	Electrical conductivity
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
GPS	Global Positioning System
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
ISE	Ion-selective electrode
IT	Information Technology
JRA	Joint research activities
LED	Light emitting diode
Lidar	Light detection and ranging
LoQ	Limit of quantification
LPICM	Low-power Inductive Conductivity Monitor
NH ₄ -N	Ammonium nitrogen
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon
PFA	Polyfluoroalkyl substance
PLS	Partial Least Squares
PLS	Partial least square
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
RGB	Red green blue
RGB	Red Green Blue
RI	Research infrastructure
RMSE	Root mean squared error
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SSIV	Surface Structure Image Velocimetry
STW	Severn Trent Water
SuDS	Sustainable Drainage Systems

SVM	Support vector machine
TA	Transnational access
TRL	Technology readiness level
UDMT	Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox
UDS	Urban Drainage System
UV-vis	Ultraviolet and visible
VNIR	Visible and near-infrared
WTW	Wastewater treatment works

Executive summary

Urbanization and climate change place increasing pressure on urban drainage systems (UDS) and natural aquatic ecosystems. Smart monitoring and IT are crucial for designing, operating, and upgrading UDS to protect and improve ecosystem quality. However, Europe lacks reliable information on UDS performance and pollutant emissions. Most currently installed sensors in UDS are related to hydraulic measurements, e.g., to detect overflows, measure levels in tanks and pipes, flows, etc., and do not give the necessary information on pollutants, ecological impacts of emissions, and asset condition.

This deliverable (D6.2) provides a detailed report on the testing of eight emerging sensor technologies for monitoring pollutants, water quality, and the condition of UDS assets. We evaluated the sensors in both controlled laboratory conditions and real-world UDS settings. The testing aimed to assess the technical performance of these sensors in measuring parameters such as coliforms, flow, pollutants like ammonium and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and even sediment levels using LiDAR technology. In addition to evaluating the technical performance of the sensors, we also assessed their operational performance, including factors such as the need for maintenance and the complexity of the calibration procedure.

In this report, we outline the testing methodology, which includes a structured approach to sensor selection and evaluation. It provides detailed results on sensor performance, highlighting both promising outcomes and limitations. Several sensors, such as the LPICM and ISA, showed potential for real-world applications, demonstrating their ability to reliably monitor UDS parameters. However, not all sensors performed as expected, with some, like the PAH probe, failing to deliver reliable data on pollutants. These results underscore the importance of rigorous testing and validation, particularly in real-world conditions.

The deliverable also emphasizes the need for ongoing research and development in the field of UDS monitoring, as not all sensors are yet at the technological readiness level required for widespread implementation. We intend to use the findings from this work to guide future research projects and assist practitioners in making informed decisions when selecting sensors for UDS applications.

Furthermore, the datasets generated from this research are openly available¹, contributing to the broader goal of fostering transparency and collaboration in the urban water management community. The findings also align with the strategic goals of the Co-UDlabs project, including the support of evidence-based management and the development of a more resilient and sustainable Water Smart Society.

¹ The datasets will be made available on Zenodo early 2025, so that all required links are updated in this report's section 6 for M48.

1. Introduction

Effective water management is dependent on robust water quality monitoring systems. Accurate and reliable monitoring allows for timely and informed decision-making, accurate evaluation of public health and environmental risks as well as provides confidence in regulatory compliance which are based on water quality metrics (Chawla et al., 2020). Recent EU regulations on surface and groundwater pollution emphasize the need for improved accessibility and usability of chemical monitoring data to inform policies addressing emerging challenges (EC, 2024). Among these challenges, urban drainage systems (UDS) face increasing pressure from urbanization and climate change, which exacerbate the complexity of managing water quality and protecting aquatic ecosystems (Razguliaev et al., 2024).

Smart monitoring technologies and data-driven strategies are essential to meet these challenges, yet reliable information on UDS performance and pollutant emissions remains scarce across Europe. The transition to a more open, digital and evidence-based management approach requires not only the deployment of advanced sensors but also improvements in their ability to capture pollutants, ecological impacts, and system conditions. Existing sensors often focus on hydraulic parameters, leaving critical gaps in monitoring pollutants, pathogens, ecological impacts, and asset conditions. Additionally, many sensor signals suffer from poor data quality, and urban drainage utilities are not fully prepared for the digital water revolution (Bertrand-Krajewski et al., 2021).

Furthermore, traditional monitoring methods can be slow, labor-intensive (e.g., requiring frequent calibration), limited in scope, and unable to capture the full complexity of water pollution. It is particularly challenging to measure chemical pollutants of emerging concerns and pathogens, necessitating the development of more sensitive and rapid detection and tracking methods (Elgarahy et al., 2024). Consequently, our understanding of many emerging contaminants in water bodies remains incomplete, and we have yet to establish their full environmental and health risks. These include pharmaceuticals, microplastics, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAs). Improvements in monitoring and sensing technologies are therefore critical to understanding the distribution, fate, and transformation of pollutants in UDS as well as the wider environment. Addressing these gaps requires new technologies that are low-cost, deployable, and robust, but also necessitates independent testing to evaluate their performance, costs, suitability for deployment and limitations.

Task 6.1 of the Co-UDlabs project (WP6) aims to support the transition to a digital, evidence-based decision-making process by i) reviewing emerging sensor technologies, ii) selecting the most promising ones, and iii) evaluating their performance in the laboratory and, most importantly, real urban drainage systems. In deliverable D6.1, we provided an overview of the reviewed innovative sensor technologies, presented the 8 selected sensors, and outlined their planned testing (Rieckermann, 2022).

In this report, deliverable D6.2, we present the outcome of the subsequent work on testing methodology and discuss the achieved results of testing the 8 sensors both in the laboratory and in real-world conditions. This report provides a summary report for both future research projects and potential users of the technologies tested. Although the in-depth testing revealed promising results for most of the sensors, not all were capable to provide the necessary data on pollutants

and ecological impacts. Also, not all sensors are available at the required technological readiness level for wastewater operators. The datasets from the work produced in this deliverable are openly available.²

2. Methods: unified approach for sensor testing

2.1. Sensor selection

The selection of promising sensing technologies for urban drainage monitoring followed a three-step structure described in detail in D6.1 (Rieckermann, 2022). First, the members of the consortium compiled a list of 55 potential sensors and digital technologies. We focused on technologies for monitoring water quality, detecting pollutants, managing solids, and tracking assets in urban drainage systems. We categorized sensors based on their capacity to measure emerging pollutants, provide low-cost solutions, or offer higher spatio-temporal resolution. Second, Eawag and INSA narrowed the list based on criteria such as scientific novelty, technological readiness level (TRL), and practical feasibility (cost and availability). This process narrowed the list to 15 sensors, which included primarily water quality sensors, with the exclusion of "other" technologies like IoT transmission devices. Third, members of the consortium expressed their interest in testing the remaining sensors, ranking them on a scale from 0 (not interested) to 4 (willing to develop). The final selection of 8 sensors was based on averaging these scores. This list included sensors for coliform measurement, low-power conductivity, water flow, pollutants like ammonium and PAHs, and 3D sediment mapping using LiDAR, as summarized in Table 1.

2.2. Testing plan

We followed a two-step testing procedure, where the eight technologies were first tested by members of the consortium. If this first phase of testing was promising, the sensors were sent to another location for a second and independent phase of tests (see Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of the 8 tested sensors and of the testing institutions for test phases 1 and 2.

Sensor Number	Sensor name	Measured parameter	First phase of test	Second phase of test
1	Proteus	Coliform concentration	UoS	<i>none</i>
2	LPICM	Conductivity	Eawag	3 sewer systems in Switzerland
3	DischargeKeeper	Flow	Eawag	UDC
4	ISA spectrometer	Multi – UV-visible absorbance	Eawag	UDC
5	MV.X hyperspectral imager	Multi – VNIR reflectance	Eawag	Monash University, Australia
6	PAH probe	PAH	INSA	<i>none</i>
7	Pipe Mapping FSB	Pipe mapping	INSA	<i>none</i>
8	3D Lidar Sediment Mapping	Sediment mapping	Deltares	<i>none</i>

² The datasets will be made available on Zenodo early 2025, so that all required links are updated in this report's section 6 for M48.

At the end of the first phase of testing, we decided to continue testing four out of the eight sensors, while the PAH probe and the Proteus performances were not sufficient to justify further testing. Sections 3.1 and 3.2 provide detailed explanations on why we decided to stop testing those two technologies. We also had to abandon the second phase of testing of the Pipe mapping FSB and 3D Lidar sediment mapping, which only one institution had tested (see sections 3.7 and 3.8), due to resource constraints and limited availability of personnel.

For each series of tests, we prioritize experiments in field conditions or pilot scale facilities. When field conditions or pilot scale facilities were not feasible, we evaluated the sensors in a laboratory setup. Each test required at least 20 reference values measured with a state-of-the-art method to assess the sensor's performance. Finally, we designed the experiments to run for at least one week to confront the tested technology with a broader range of conditions.

2.3. Data validation

Data validation is a key aspect of metrology and monitoring. It has been applied to some tested sensors by using the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT) developed in Task 6.2 (Bertrand-Krajewski and Lepot, 2023). The online version of the UDMT is openly accessible³, as well as the exe version that can be installed on any offline computer⁴ (Bertrand-Krajewski and Lepot, 2023).

Data validation in the UDMT includes various automated tests aiming to check ranges and to detect outliers, unusual values, and suspicious evolutions (gradients, peaks, constant values, etc.) in time series. The output is a final qualification of each data point with three possible grades: valid, not valid, or doubtful, the latter requiring a further investigation by the user to decide between valid and not valid final qualifications. The basic tests implemented in the UDMT allow checking if the data are

- within the physical range, i.e., within the measuring range of the sensor.
- within the measuring range, i.e., within the physical boundaries of the measured phenomena in a given location.
- within the expert range, i.e., within the measuring range an expert considers as valid for a given sensor installed in a given location under some given conditions.
- within the expected gradient range, i.e., the variations of the values are not abnormally fast or slow.
- affected by uncertainties higher than the maximum acceptable absolute uncertainty.
- affected by relative uncertainties higher than the maximum acceptable relative uncertainty.
- compatible with redundant data, i.e., with other measured or calculated data that are supposed to be close to the data under evaluation.
- outliers, or not.

³ <http://vps-7bc5cf87.vps.ovh.net:9988/webapps/home/session.html?app=coudlabs>

⁴ <https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V>

The tests described above cannot be applied to all sensors; their applicability depends on the availability of specific information, data, and expertise. For instance, while determining the measuring range is straightforward (as it corresponds to the sensor's operational range provided by the manufacturer), defining the physical or expert range requires knowledge of the typical or most frequent values expected at a specific monitoring location. Redundancy tests cannot be conducted without access to a redundant or highly correlated sensor. Similarly, tests based on uncertainties necessitate a preliminary evaluation of the uncertainties associated with the measured values, which are influenced by both the sensor and the measurement conditions. The user manual (Bertrand-Krajewski and Lepot, 2023) provides detailed guidance on the data and file formats required for UDMT data validation. An example application of UDMT data validation is presented in Section 4.

2.4. Sensor evaluation

We designed an evaluation sheet to compile, for each technology tested, the following information: (i) general information, (ii) manufacturer technical information, (iii) testing information, (iv) technical performances, and (v) operational performances.

General information

This section of the testing sheet contains data about the sensor name, model, measured parameter, manufacturer, sensing principle, TRL, and a link to the sensor's or the manufacturer's webpage. For the TRL, we utilized a scale similar to the one used in deliverable D6.1 (Rieckermann, 2022), which we adapted from the European Commission's definition (EC, 2017). This scale ranges from 1 to 5, where 1 represents an in-house experimental prototype and 5 represents a commercially available sensor.

Manufacturer technical information

This section includes, when available, information about the measurement range and accuracy of the sensor, as given by the sensor manufacturer or a scientific reference that tested it.

Testing information

This section provides background about how the sensing technology was tested in the Co-UDlabs project. It includes testing duration (in days), number of reference measurements, and the type of environment in which the technology was validated (laboratory, pilot, or field conditions). Finally, we summarized into an “overall quality/reliability of testing” indicator the quality of the testing conditions. This indicator is defined as a number between 1 and 5, with 1 defined as low reliability (few numbers of samples, tested in laboratory conditions, limited range, etc.) and 5 as high reliability (high number of samples, tested in field conditions, broad range, etc.).

Technical performances

The section comprises a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators. It includes quantitative indicators such as the tested range, the expressed accuracy in root mean squared error (RMSE) between sensor and reference measurements, and the percentage of data completeness. Data completeness is defined as the percentage of data after validation, showing how well the sensor can provide valid measurements. We used different qualitative indicators,

such as whether the drifts are present (yes/no), whether the accuracy meets UDS needs (1: the accuracy is too low for UDS use; 5: the accuracy is suitable), whether the range meets UDS needs (1: the tested range is small compared to the values seen in UDS; 5: the tested range matches the typical UDS range), and the overall technical performances (1: poor performances; 5: excellent performances).

Operational performances

The operational performance compiles 7 quantitative indicators, as described in Table 2.

Table 2: Quantitative indicators used for the evaluation of the operational performances of the tested technologies (1: poor, 5: excellent).

Attribute	Range	Description
Overall operational performance	1-5	1: poor performance; 5: excellent performance
Ease of calibration	1-5	1: costly in time (>1 h) and resources (use of chemicals, experts, etc.); 5: quick and inexpensive
Frequency of calibration required	1-5	1: more than once a week; 3: once a month; 5: yearly scale
Ease of maintenance	1-5	1: costly in time (>1 h) and resources (use of chemicals, experts, etc.); 5: quick and inexpensive
Frequency of maintenance required	1-5	1: more than once a week; 3: once a month; 5: yearly scale
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)	1-5	1: not suitable; 3: suitable with modification; 5: suitable
ATEX	yes/no	

We decided to use quantitative indicators with the goal of comparing the sensors with each other and providing a simplified overview of the performances. We harmonized the evaluation to ensure consistency in each sensor's rating. In addition, the evaluation sheet includes a comment column in which we provide written justifications for the rating when necessary. All testing sheets are available in Appendix A.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sensor 1: Proteus

Sensor description and testing

The Proteus is a commercially available multi-parameter water quality probe provided by RS Instruments, procured by Severn Trent Water (STW), and deployed in the Leam catchment (UK) within the river system, directly next to the drinking water abstraction intake. The probe was installed to provide real-time warning of high bacterial loads/poor water quality to the water treatment works (WTW). The initial installation of the probe was carried out in April 2021.

The sensor utilizes a fluorometer to measure tryptophan-like fluorescence *in situ* to derive the total coliforms or the E. coli levels, using a relationship/correlation derived through calibration. Turbidity and temperature serve as additional parameters for tryptophan compensation, along with optical brighteners. To achieve a site-specific calibration, we followed the manufacturer's recommended calibration protocol for accurate and repeatable measurement of the derived parameters. Table 3 provides the date, sampling durations, rainfall, and river flow characteristics of each testing event. We conducted an initial test (E0) under dry weather flow conditions, comparing the probe readings to reference values obtained from repeated spot sampling at the abstraction site, and analysed them using standard methods at the WTW laboratory. Following this initial test, we carried out sampling during rainfall runoff events at the same location as the Proteus sensor to cover bacterial loading across a range of rainfall-runoff events. In this case, a Severn Trent laboratory analysed river water samples for the presence of total coliforms and E. coli. This involved collecting samples every two hours during the high-flow event, which occurred after a rainfall event. After the calibration event (E1), we sampled 3 additional events (E2 - E4) to evaluate and test the sensor. We collected these samples under various rainfall events and seasonal conditions.

Table 3: E. coli sampling event dates, durations and sampling frequencies. Rainfall duration is based on analysis of radar rainfall data from the UK MET office.

Event No.	Start date	Sampling duration (h)	Sampling frequency (h)	Rainfall event duration (h)	River flow (m ³ /s)	
					Max	Min
E0	19.09.2021	24 h	1	0	0.240	0.226
E1	03.12.2021	82 h	2	8	5.850	0.369
E2	05.02.2022	114 h	2	32	2.530	0.575
E3	16.08.2022	46 h	2	9	0.389	0.225
E4	12.03.2023	68 h	1	41	31.800	0.272

Live data from the probe was provided by telemetry and hosted online. This project had access to the post-processed data. Specific calibration relationships are currently commercially sensitive and are the property of RS instruments. Hence all calibration and quality assurance were undertaken by RS instruments staff, with limited input by the project team.

An autosampler was used to collect all water samples for subsequent culture analysis and its intake was set up as close to the location of the sensors as possible without obstructing the flow of water to and from the sensors. Ice was used to keep samples cool while in the autosampler and a refrigerated cool box with ice was used during the 1 hour, twice a day, transportation of samples for analysis to the WTW laboratory at Church Wilne. The samples were analysed using membrane filtration method as stated in the Standing Committee of Analysts (2016) based on Sartory and Howard (1992). Raw river water at the study site had very high concentrations of bacteria and particules, as demonstrated by a grab sample analysed to assess the range of dilutions needed, prior to the main sampling event. Therefore, it was judged necessary to analyse sample volumes ranging from 10 mL down to 0.01 mL. For serial dilutions of 0.1 and 0.01 mL a portion of the sample is added to a Maximum Recovery Solution to prepare a serial 10-fold

dilution series. The water sample is then filtered through a cellulose acetate membrane filter upon which bacteria are entrapped. The filter is then placed on a selective growth medium and incubated at $30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 ± 0.25 hours followed by $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 17 ± 3 hours. After incubation is complete the colonies, which are characteristic of Coliforms and *Escherichia coli* are counted.

Results and discussion

Figure 1: *E. coli* concentration measured by the calibrated sensor and in laboratory, and rainfall for the events E0-E5.

Calibration results (event E1). The high-flow event E1 was used for sensor calibration, as shown in Figure 1b. This dataset, provided by RS Instruments staff, allowed for model training using surrogate parameters to derive *E. coli* levels. Lab analysis indicated that *E. coli* levels started at 130 CFU/100 mL, peaking at 12,000 CFU/100 mL and 6,800 CFU/100 mL during two distinct peaks. The calibrated sensor data displayed a good fit to lab data, achieving an R^2 value of 0.932 (Figure 2). However, the sensor failed to capture the full magnitude of *E. coli* peaks during subsequent validation events, as detailed below.

Figure 2: Calibration result plot for event E1 (provided by RS instrument).

Baseline condition monitoring (event E0). Figure 1a presents data from event E0, which was used to establish baseline bacterial levels under conditions unaffected by acute rainfall impacts. For event E0, hourly samples were collected over a 24-hour period in mid-September 2021. The retrospectively calibrated sensor data for this event revealed a significant offset during baseline conditions. This discrepancy is likely due to the calibration models being trained on data from high-flow events with acute *E. coli* peaks (e.g., event E1, Figure 1b). As expected, no discernible trends were observed in the data due to the absence of rainfall-driven inputs into the river. Laboratory measurements of *E. coli* levels for this event ranged from 330 to 700 CFU/100 mL, classifying the water quality as "excellent" to "good" for inland bathing waters.

Validation events (E2, E3, and E4). Figure 1c, d and e show the performance of the calibrated sensor during validation events E2, E3, and E4.

- Event E2: Lab analysis recorded initial *E. coli* levels of 2,100 CFU/100 mL, with peaks reaching 43,000 CFU/100 mL and 17,000 CFU/100 mL.
- Event E3: Starting at 200 CFU/100 mL, *E. coli* levels escalated to 17,000 CFU/100 mL and 5,800 CFU/100 mL during two distinct peaks.
- Event E4: This event exhibited more complex dynamics, with *E. coli* levels ranging from 3,800 CFU/100 mL to a peak of 42,000 CFU/100 mL. The calibrated sensor missed the first half of the elevated *E. coli* levels, highlighting significant limitations in capturing variability.

Figure 3 provides an overview of the sensor's overall performance against lab-derived measurements, emphasizing challenges in accurately representing peak *E. coli* concentrations.

Figure 3: Validation result plot for events E2-E4

Challenges in sensor calibration across events. The contrasting performance of the sensor across events (E1–E4) underscores its difficulty in deriving E. coli levels under conditions involving complex and highly variable supply sources. Relying on calibration models developed from a single event (e.g., E1) proved inadequate for accurately predicting conditions in other scenarios. These findings highlight the need for multi-event calibration to improve sensor reliability across diverse conditions.

Further details about the study site, testing methodology, and additional data can be found in Susloviate (2023).

3.2. Sensor 2: PAH

A detailed report about the PAH sensor testing is available in Appendix B.

Sensor description and testing

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) form a group of organic molecules frequently detected and quantified in stormwater runoff at levels ranging from ng/L to µg/L depending on the molecule (e.g. Becouze-Lareure et al., 2019). The Trios EnviroFlu-HC (Figure 4) has been identified as a potentially interesting sensor to measure PAHs in stormwater. It estimates concentrations of PAHs in the range 0-500 ppb (or µg/L) by means of fluorescence. A xenon lamp light source illuminates the water volume near the probe at 254 nm and the backscattered fluorescence is measured by a photodiode at 360 nm. The estimated concentration is then converted into a 4-20 mA analogic signal. The manufacturer indicates the probe can be used in drinking water, wastewater, airports, refineries, etc. with the following specifications: detection limit 0.3 ppb, measurement accuracy ± 5% of full scale, reproducibility ≤ 0.5% of full scale, response time ≤ 10 s, measurement interval ≥ 5 s, no turbidity compensation. The complete sensor data sheet is available at <https://www.trios.de/en/enviroflu.html> (consulted on 06 Nov 2024).

Figure 4: Trios EnviroFlu-HC 500 probe (source: Trios company website).

Testing site. The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor was tested in the Chassieu catchment in Lyon, France. The Chassieu catchment is a 185-ha industrial area in the eastern suburbs of Lyon (45°44'10.30"N/4°57'31.27"E) drained by a separate stormwater sewer system. The catchment mean slope is 0.4 % and its active area is 54 ha. At the catchment outlet (Figure 5), a set of sensors allows continuous monitoring (with a 2 min time step) of water depth and flow velocity. A peristaltic pump continuously feeds at approx. 0.7 L/s a monitoring flume in a shelter located above the outlet sewer (Figure 5 left) with water circulating in the sewer during storm events (there is also a small and intermittent dry weather flow in the sewer due to industrial cooling activities in the catchment). Water quality parameters (pH, conductivity, turbidity, temperature) are measured (with a 2-minutes time step) with online sensors in the monitoring flume (Figure 5 right). Automatic samplers are also installed in the shelter to collect samples at defined time or volume intervals.

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor was installed in the Chassieu monitoring flume for testing (Figure 6 left), where some accidental hydrocarbons spills are occasionally observed (Figure 6 right), in addition to the systematic presence of PAHs during storm events (Becouze-Lareure et al., 2019).

Figure 5: Left: scheme of the shelter equipment (source: INSA); right: monitoring flume with sensors in the shelter (source: Nicolas Walcker).

Figure 6: Left and middle: the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor at the end of testing in the Chassieu monitoring flume; right: accidental spill of hydrocarbons at the outlet of the Chassieu catchment (sources: Nicolas Walcker).

Methods for sensor testing. The sensor testing included two parts: 1) laboratory correlation and 2) *in situ* continuous data collection.

Laboratory correlation. The laboratory test aimed to compare i) the concentration values delivered by the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor immersed in samples collected in Chassieu during storm events, with ii) the PAHs concentrations of the same samples measured by the external accredited Carso laboratory. Once the samples were grabbed, 240 measurements were recorded immediately on site, with the same data acquisition system as the one running 24/7 in the shelter. Samples were then transported to the laboratory and half of the volume was filtrated with a 0.45 µm paper filter to get latter analyses on both total (T) and dissolved (D) PAH concentrations. Finally, raw and filtrated samples were sent to Carso laboratory and analysed according to their method M_ET283 (gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry), delivering concentrations of 30 PAH molecules with limits of quantification varying from 0.005 to 0.05 µg/L (Table 4), i.e. from 0.001 to 0.01 % of the Trios EnviroFlu-HC full scale. In total, nine samples have been collected during two storm events on 07 and 17 Jan. 2023: three samples have been analysed only for the dissolved fraction (D), and six for the total sample (T).

Table 4: List of the 30 PAH molecules measured by Carso laboratory, with the corresponding Limit of Quantification (LoQ).

ID nr.	PAH molecule	LoQ* (µg/L)	ID nr.	PAH molecule	LoQ* (µg/L)
1	2-methyl fluoranthene	0.005	16	Fluorene*	0.005
2	1-methyl naphtalene	0.005	17	Naphtalene*	0.02
3	2-methyl naphtalene	0.02	18	Pyrene*	0.005
4	Acenaphtene*	0.005	19	Phenanthrene*	0.02
5	Acenaphtylene*	0.01	20	Anthraquinone	0.05
6	Anthracene*	0.005	21	Benzo (j) fluoranthene	0.005
7	Benzo (a) anthracene*	0.005	22	Benzo (e) pyrene	0.005
8	Benzo (b) fluoranthene*	0.005	23	Coronene	0.05
9	Benzo (k) fluoranthene*	0.005	24	Dibenzo (a,e) pyrene	0.05
10	Benzo (a) pyrene*	0.005	25	Dibenzo (a,i) pyrene	0.05
11	Benzo (g,h,i) perylene*	0.005	26	Dibenzo (a,h) pyrene	0.05
12	Indeno (1,2,3 cd) pyrene*	0.005	27	Dibenzo (a,l) pyrene	0.05
13	Chrysene*	0.005	28	Dekalin (decahydronaphtalene)	0.02
14	Fluoranthene*	0.005	29	Benzo (c) phenanthrene	0.005
15	Dibenzo (a,h) anthracene*	0.005	30	Anthanthrene	0.005

* indicates a priority PAH molecule.

In situ data collection. The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor has been installed in the flume of the Chassieu retention OTHU monitoring station (Figure 5 and Figure 6), from 30 May 2022 at 12:10 until 31 Dec. 2022 at 23:58. Its data have been collected with a 2-min time step. It was checked during the usual weekly maintenance visits.

Results and discussion

Laboratory correlation. Figure 7 displays the sensor concentrations versus the laboratory concentrations. It appears immediately that sensor concentrations are 2 orders of magnitude larger than the laboratory concentrations and are much higher than PAHs concentrations reported in the literature. It seems that the sensor substantially overestimates the PAHs concentrations. Looking at the 6 grey points corresponding to measurements of total samples (T), one observes that the correlation is negative, which is not plausible ($r = -0.4239$). The regression line is $C_{\text{sensor}} = b_1 + b_2 \cdot C_{\text{lab}}$, with $b_1 = 59.7745$ and $b_2 = -40.3225$. This regression is however extremely approximate as i) it is based only on 6 points, ii) the coefficients b_i are highly uncertain with 95% coverage intervals respectively equal to [4.6068, 114.9421] and [-159.9265, 79.2814], and iii) an RMSE value equal to 26.6709 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The 3 light blue points corresponding to measurements of dissolved fractions (D) do not show better results in terms of correlation with the sensor values. In addition, laboratory concentrations of dissolved fractions (D) are consistent, as they are globally much lower than those measured on total samples (D), which corroborates the information in literature indicating that most PAHs are observed in the particulate fraction in stormwater runoff (e.g. Becouze-Lareure et al., 2019 and Herngren et al., 2010). This trend is not observed with the concentrations given by the sensor.

Figure 7: Plot of Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor concentrations vs. Carso laboratory PAHs concentrations, with regression line for total sample concentrations.

In situ data collection. From 30 May 2022 12:10 to 31 Dec. 2022 23:58, the feeding pump was ‘on’ during 321.7 h in total only, i.e. 6.2% of the time, mainly during storm events as expected. The data collected *in situ* during the periods the feeding pump was ‘on’ are displayed in Figure 8. During storm events, at first glance the PAH sensor concentration varies consistently with discharge and turbidity, despite frequent saturation of the PAH sensor (example of period 14 to

30 Nov. 2022 in Appendix B). At the individual storm event scale (example of storm event dated 28-30 Nov. 2022 in Appendix B), the above statement is confirmed: when the sensor saturation and high peaks are masked, the rest of the PAH sensor data (in the range 0-80 $\mu\text{g/L}$) and their evolution are to some extent similar to the turbidity data. This may be partly explained by the fact that the PAH sensor has no turbidity compensation and seems to be very strongly affected by this quantity. However, this is not confirmed by the absence of correlation between turbidity and PAH sensor concentration: $r = 0.0257$.

Figure 8: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 30 May to 31 Dec. 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: outlet discharge, b: turbidity, c: PAH concentration.

In addition, the order of magnitude of the PAH concentration, as shown in laboratory correlation, is unrealistic for PAHs concentrations in stormwater. As reported in literature, a possible explanation is that the PAH sensor may be affected by interference from other molecules, e.g. like humic acids, also present in stormwater, which are contributing to fluorescence (e.g. Bressy et al., 2014). Any molecule with a structure similar to PAH molecules structures may generate a response in fluorescence: in other words, it is difficult, in a water matrix containing a great diversity of organic molecules, to have a selective PAH probe (Wiest, 2023).

Conclusions. The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor does not seem to be reliably used directly for online measurements of PAH concentration in stormwater due to i) lack of correlation and large difference in order of magnitude between sensor data and PAH laboratory analyses in the same samples; and ii) difficulty to relate *in situ* measurements with diverse PAH molecules due to possible interferences with other molecules in stormwater and the fact that PAHs in stormwater are mainly observed in the particulate phase.

3.3. Sensor 3: LPICM

Sensor description and testing

Introduction. Monitoring electrical conductivity (EC) is critical for understanding processes such as pollutant dynamics and groundwater infiltration in wastewater systems. Conductivity serves as a proxy for pollution levels and has been useful for studying infiltration, pollutant concentrations, loads, and event-based fluxes in urban wastewater and stormwater (Schilperoort et al., 2006 and Obenaus et al., 1999).

In sewer system applications, conductivity sensors with high temporal resolution are ideal. However, conductive systems face limitations due to environmental conditions, like corrosion and deposits on electrodes, leading to inaccurate measurements. As an alternative, inductive conductivity sensors are more robust in harsh environments, making them less susceptible to contamination. Yet, these sensors typically require a stable power supply, which makes long-term, battery-operated deployment in remote areas challenging.

A promising development addressing these issues is the Low-Power Inductive Conductivity Monitor (LPICM) by Eawag and HSR/OST (Grab and Barbisch, 2018). The LPICM offers several key advantages:

- **Low-power:** The device boasts low power consumption, as it can take conductivity and temperature measurements every 15 minutes for over a year on two Li-Ion AA batteries.
- **Connectivity:** The device supports LoRaWAN wireless data transfer, making it suitable for IoT applications. The device also stores data on an SD card for redundancy.
- **Open platform:** The design allows for easy future modifications and improvements.
- **Protection:** The sensor has a custom shield of stainless steel to prevent clogging in harsh environments and keep the sensor submerged.

However, a possible limitation of the LPICM is the response time of the InPro7250 sensor head (Mettler Toledo, Greifensee, CH) of about 5 minutes, due to its heavy-duty casing. As it is an in-house prototype, the current hardware is not ATEX certified, although the “High Temperature” model of the InPro7250 is ATEX certified.

In the testing phase, we aimed to address two key study questions:

1. What is the potential of the LPICM as an online proxy for ammonium?
2. Can we use it to evaluate wastewater dilution ratios during wet weather?

Methods for sensor testing. The LPICM was tested in the Eawag experimental hall (Dübendorf, Switzerland) between May and November 2023, and in Swiss full-scale sewer systems at Zug (since 2021), at Lenzburg and Rheinach (15.02.2024-04.04.2024), in total for more than 3 years under real-world conditions. In this report, we present the results from Eawag and Lenzburg, and the results from the other sites are available in Rieckermann (2025). At Lenzburg, the LPICM was first installed 1.5 years at the inlet of the wastewater treatment plant, before being installed 4 months in the sewer network.

Figure 1: Experimental Setup for Dilution test

Figure 5: Experimental Setup in the Primary Clarifier

Figure 9: Impressions of different sensor tests in the lab (top left), pilot reactors (top right) and full-scale sewer systems of Lenzburg (bottom left). Sensor head gets after immersion in wastewater (bottom right).

At Eawag, the sensor was installed in the small primary clarifier of the hall wastewater treatment plant (see Figure 9) which continuously received raw wastewater from a nearby sewer (catchment: 25.000 Population Equivalent). The sensor measured conductivity every 5 minutes during the experiment. We calibrated the probe with local wastewaters and found that it was stable and has an excellent linear relation between EC and output voltage. To avoid clogging around the sensor head, the sensor was equipped with a custom shield, which was originally PVC and is now stainless steel (Rieckermann, 2025). Furthermore, the sensor was cleaned irregularly (weekly or once every two-three weeks) by the operational personnel of each utility.

To assess the suitability of EC as a surrogate for ammonium, an ion-selective electrode (ISE) was installed to measure ammonium (Aerts and Blumensaat, 2021). Those reference measurements were used to calibrate and validate the LPICM performance.

Pre-processing of online data. Initially, the collected data was pre-processed, starting with a verification of the timestamps. Next, the majority of the cleaned dataset was used to train the model to predict ammonium nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$) values based on electrical conductivity and discharge measurements. Finally, the predicted results were compared with the remaining portion of the cleaned original dataset to assess the model's accuracy.

Results and discussion

Figure 10 show the results of the EC-ammonium models for Eawag ($R^2 = 0.64$), Lenzburg treatment plant ($R^2 = 0.49$) and Lenzburg sewers ($R^2 = 0.52$). Predicting $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentrations using electrical conductivity measurements is inherently difficult due to the unpredictable nature of wastewater generation and the variability introduced by industrial and household discharges

(Blumensaat, 2020). These fluctuations create disturbances in the data, leading to generally low correlations between EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, with R^2 values typically ranging from 0.4 to 0.6. The stochastic behaviour of wastewater flow, influenced by various sources and unpredictable pollutant loads, complicates the ability to establish a consistent predictive relationship.

However, during wet weather events, the relationship between EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ appears to be more stable (red data points), albeit within a narrower range. This is likely due to the dilution effect of stormwater, which reduces the variability of pollutant concentrations. While this stabilization during rainfall may help improve the predictability of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ levels, the overall correlation remains limited by the small range of values, meaning that even under these conditions, the predictive power of EC measurements is constrained.

Figure 10: EC-ammonium models in Eawag (a), Lenzburg treatment plant (b) and Lenzburg sewers (c). The relationship during wet weather is shown in red.

EC measurements can generally be used to identify the dilution of wastewater by rainwater, as electrical conductivity tends to decrease with the influx of rainfall runoff. This makes EC a useful parameter for detecting rainfall impacts on sewer systems, possibly also for pollution-based Real-Time Control. However, at this particular monitoring location, an intriguing pattern emerged: during dry weather conditions, the peaks of EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ were consistently offset. This systematic shift indicates that some underlying process is influencing the temporal alignment of these parameters.

Although the exact cause of this shift remains unclear, one plausible explanation is the influence of ion exchangers within the system, which may undergo rehabilitation during nighttime hours. Ion exchangers are used in water treatment to remove specific ions, and their regeneration process could temporarily alter the concentration of ions in the wastewater, thus affecting both

EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ levels. This nightly process may explain the observed temporal displacement between conductivity and ammonium concentrations (horizontal arrows in Figure 11).

Figure 11: Comparison of the ISE ammonium and LPCIM conductivity for the Lenzburg data between 04/03/2020 and 06/03/2020, showing a time shift between peaks of EC and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ during dry weather.

In this study, the LPCIM provided useful insights into how electrical conductivity changes with wastewater dilution, particularly when rainwater enters sewer systems. During rainfall events, the sensor recorded clear drops in conductivity, reflecting the lower ionic content of incoming stormwater. This finding is valuable for understanding and managing combined sewer overflows and refining pollutant load models.

However, the results also indicate that using conductivity alone as a direct proxy for ammonium concentration is problematic. Although we observed some correlation during rain events, dry weather dynamics and unexpected conductivity spikes—possibly linked to industrial activity—made these relationships unreliable. Predictive models based solely on conductivity performed poorly in estimating absolute ammonium levels (Heller, 2023). These limitations suggest that conductivity measurements need to be combined with additional parameters to improve accuracy (Obenaus et al., 1999). Including factors like turbidity, which can serve as a surrogate for suspended solids, might enhance our understanding of pollution patterns and lead to better tools for managing wastewater quality under diverse environmental conditions (Schilperoort et al., 2006).

Finally, it is encouraging to see that sensors we once designed and conceptualized are now entering the market. Low-power inductive monitors are now becoming available from pioneering manufactures⁵ although they are missing the effective clogging protection of our prototype. The

⁵ https://www.ijinus.com/produit/by-activity-en-en-en/environment-en/data-logger-physico-chemical/?lang=en#tab-description_tab

emergence of low-power inductive sensors for wastewater monitoring highlights the growing recognition of water quality issues and the increasing demand in practice.

3.4. Sensor 4: ISA

Sensor description and testing

Introduction. The ISA probe (Go-Systemelektronik, Germany) is a sensor able to monitor a variety of parameters, such as chemical oxygen demand (COD), nitrate, total suspended solids, biological oxygen demand, and dissolved organic carbon. The sensing principle is based on ultraviolet and visible (UV-vis) spectrophotometry, and a data-driven model is calibrated to retrieve target parameters. The sensor, made of stainless steel, measures absorbance in the 200 to 706 nm range with a 2 nm resolution. It is therefore suitable for the monitoring of wastewater applications. The ISA sensor's flexibility allows it to monitor any parameter that directly or indirectly alters the UV-vis absorbance spectra. Pacheco et al. (2020) demonstrated that the ISA sensor can monitor ammonium in wastewater with a relative RMSE of less than 10%. Monitoring ammonium could improve the management and treatment of urban wastewater, but it is still challenging in UDS. As ammonium is known to be causing no effect on the UV-vis absorbance (Chen et al., 2019), we decided to test Pacheco's results for the Co-UDlabs project, as well as evaluate the potential of the ISA for future UDS applications.

Methods for sensor testing. The ISA was tested in the Eawag experimental hall (Dübendorf, Switzerland) between May and November 2023 and in the Campus SUDS facility at the University de Coruña (UDC) between February and August 2024.

At Eawag, we installed the sensor in a flume (see Figure 12a), which continuously received raw wastewater from a nearby sewer (catchment: 25,000 Population Equivalent). The sensor measured absorbance spectra every two minutes during the experiment. We calibrated the probe with local wastewater samples and found the optimal optical path length to be 4 mm. We connected the sensor to a pressurized air system that blasted air every 12 minutes to prevent clogging around the measurement window. Additionally, we cleaned the sensor either weekly or every two weeks using a water jet, scrub, and ethanol. Throughout the entire experimental campaign, we collected and analysed 488 grab samples for ammonium (Flex/Lachat QC8500 Flow Injection Analysis, standard method 4500-NH₃, EPA 600/4-79-020, 1983), following filtration with Chromafil GF/PET 0.45 µm (Macherey-Nagel, Switzerland). We used those reference measurements to calibrate and validate the ISA performance for ammonium estimation. We also classified each sample during dry or wet weather using the precipitation and sewer flow data, enabling the creation of two models. We calibrated the "dry weather calibration" model using samples collected during dry days and the "wet weather calibration" model during rainy days.

At UDC, the ISA sensor was installed for verification purposes with different conditions than those initially tested at Eawag. The sensor was installed alongside pH, turbidity, and electrical conductivity (EC) probes in a pilot system designed to evaluate wastewater quality on the UDC campus (Figure 12b). The system pumps wastewater from the drainage system into a hopper, where large particles settle. From there, the wastewater flows to the measurement flume. We observed blockages in the pumping systems during the initial tests. Additionally, since the

analysis medium is wastewater, biofilm formed rapidly around the probes and sensors. To solve these two problems, we scheduled the automatic cleaning procedure every three hours, using pressurized tap water to prevent blockages in the suction pipe and probes. Once the system was fully operational, we started the monitoring campaign. The sampling period began in the second week of June 2024 and concluded in the last week of July 2024, with 59 samples collected using an autosampler. These samples were analysed in the laboratory for ammonium after filtration following the ISO 23695 method (tested with LCK303 HACH cuvettes).

a) Installation at Eawag

b) Installation at UDC

Figure 12: (a) Installation of the ISA sensor in a flume at Eawag. (b): UDC installation of the ISA and other probes in a flume.

For data analysis, we provided the measured spectra and the reference ammonium measurements to the sensor manufacturers. They calibrated a model for each dataset, based on multi-linear regression and coupled with an outlier removal procedure.

Results and discussion

Results. At Eawag, we extensively tested the sensor using around 488 reference measurements. Model performances are shown in Figure 13. We trained both a wet-weather and a dry-weather model, enabling precise ammonium estimation in both scenarios. The dry weather model has an RMSE of 4.7 mg/L, while the wet weather has an RMSE of 5.5 mg/L, despite tendentially higher ammonium concentrations during dry weather. We expect this because the daily ammonium variations during dry weather are stable and follow a repetitive pattern. Figure 14 illustrates this: the model predicts a recognizable pattern where ammonium concentration increases in the morning and slightly in the evening, coinciding with the times of day when the catchment's inhabitants urinate.

a) Eawag

b) UDC

Figure 13: Scatter plot for actual vs predicted $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentration (a) at Eawag, (b) at UDC.

Figure 14: Comparison of the laboratory measurements and the dry weather calibration during the 13/08/2023 week for the Eawag dataset, showing that the model follows the expected trend.

The wet weather model remains performant. As shown in Figure 15, it indeed performs better during rain events than the dry weather calibration, which tends to overestimate ammonium. After rain, stormwater with no ammonium is mixed with households, reducing the ammonium concentration.

Figure 15: Comparison of the performance of the dry and wet weather calibrations for a rain event, showing that the wet weather calibration performs best after the rain.

UDC collected 59 samples in the second phase of sensor testing to calibrate another model. This calibration process yielded an RMSE of 3.89 mg/L, with 9 outliers (see Figure 13b). This indicates that the model was able to fit the data reasonably well. In conclusion, the sensor worked reliably to measure ammonium levels when tested in a catchment with conditions that were different from the initial calibration at Eawag.

Discussion: suitability for UDS application. At Eawag, we had to adapt the sensor installation to avoid clogging. We first mounted a wooden piece with a hydrodynamic cylindrical shape against the left wall of the flume. Secondly, we added a bent cylindrical housing at the back of the sensor to contain the sensor cables, which were otherwise accumulating toilet paper, and to ensure a smooth flow of wastewater against it. We maintained this cylindrical element against the right wall of the flume using clamps. Without those installations, the sensor was rapidly clogging, hinting that the sensor housing design is not usable for UDS. During the data collection period at UDC, it became evident that the ISA sensor requires frequent cleaning and recalibration to maintain its accuracy and functionality. Significant challenges arise from this high maintenance demand, especially in environments that lack control. The need for constant upkeep makes the ISA sensor less suitable for deployment in remote or less accessible areas where regular maintenance cannot be guaranteed. Therefore, we recommend installing the ISA sensor primarily in controlled spaces to ensure proper maintenance and recalibration when necessary. This ensures the sensor's reliability and accuracy in detecting and measuring parameters, such as ammonium levels, thereby maximizing its effectiveness in monitoring water quality.

An innovative aspect of the ISA sensor is the possibility to adapt the length of the optical path of the measurement window. This is interesting because each application involves a unique water matrix, and having the ability to adapt the optical path length makes it possible to optimize the sensor geometry, leading to a more precise measurement. Increasing the width of the optical path length to up to 20 mm also has the benefit of facilitating the sensor maintenance, making the optical windows more accessible. However, a drawback of this feature is that it adds to the complexity of maintenance and calibration.

3.5. Sensor 5: MV.X

Sensor description and testing

Introduction. Spectral cameras have the potential to improve UDS monitoring by enabling contactless, low-maintenance, and fast monitoring of wastewater pollution. Based on the same measurement principle as absorbance spectrophotometry, i.e., the measurement interaction between light and water in a high spectral resolution, reflectance spectroscopy has never been tested to monitor raw wastewater. Preliminary laboratory tests done at Eawag showed that this technique has potential not only for the measurement of suspended particle concentrations (turbidity) but also for soluble compounds such as dissolved organic carbon or ammonium concentrations (Agustsson et al., 2014 and Lechevallier et al., 2024b). The technique is also well established for the measurement of chlorophyll, suspended solid concentration, and chemical pollutants such as heavy metals or nitrogenous compounds (Kaplan et al., 2024). For the Co-UDlabs project, we assessed the potential of a hyperspectral imager to measure turbidity.

Method. We tested an industrial hyperspectral imager (Headwall Photonics, USA). This imager is water-resistant (rated IP66 and IP67), making it suitable for use involving wastewater. It functions as a push-broom camera, employing a line scan technique to measure hyperspectral datacubes. It captures data with a spectral resolution of 2 nm spanning from 400 nm to 1000 nm, corresponding to the visible and near-infrared range. We used an LED light source (EFFI-FLEX-HIS-X2-100-910-970-TR-P1-LS-CYL-ELS-24V, Effilux, Germany) with a continuous spectrum wide-band (400–800 nm) light to illuminate the wastewater surface.

For the first series of tests, we placed the hyperspectral imager in a flume (see Figure 16). We pumped water through the channel from a nearby sewer. The hyperspectral imager measured the water surface every 30 minutes. We installed a Turbimax sensor (Endress+Hauser, Germany) in the flume to take reference turbidity measurements. We collected a total of 4645 hyperspectral acquisitions with reference turbidity measurements. More information about this experimental campaign is available in Lechevallier et al., 2024a.

Figure 16: (left) Picture of the flume used for the Eawag tests of the MV.X hyperspectral camera; (right) Drawing of the camera installation.

For the second series of tests, we collected, in collaboration with Queensland University of Technology (Australia), samples from the inlet of three wastewater treatment plants near Melbourne and one stormwater treatment creek. We conducted hyperspectral data acquisitions and turbidity measurements (Orion AQ4500, Thermo Scientific, USA) in the Monash University laboratory. We analysed a total of 188 samples in laboratory (see Figure 17).

Figure 17: (left) Picture of the Monash setup for hyperspectral data acquisition; (right) Drawing of the camera installation.

We selected a partial least squares (PLS) regression to model wastewater turbidity from hyperspectral reflectance data. This decision followed an evaluation of various regression techniques, including ensembling models and Support Vector Machine (SVM) regressors. We found that ensembling models overfit the training set, compromising their generalizability to unseen data. While SVM showed potential, PLS was systematically performing better. Furthermore, the wastewater spectra structure, characterized by high dimensionality and strong colinearity among wavelengths, is known to suit PLS (Lepot et al., 2016). We followed our previous methodology to perform wavelength selection and latent variable optimization, critical for model accuracy (Lechevallier et al., 2024b). This involved the iterative stepwise elimination PLS method for the selection of relevant wavelengths. We trained and evaluated two independent models: one for the Flume campaign and one for the Monash campaign. For model training, we used 5-fold cross-validation with 200 random samples from the flume campaign or with the 188 samples from the Monash campaign. As we had enough samples in the flume dataset, we could test the corresponding model on the 4445 remaining samples. We evaluated the model performances using two metrics: the coefficient of determination and the RMSE.

Results and discussion

Results. During model training, performed with 5-fold cross validation, both models show similar performances, as illustrated by Figure 18. With an R^2 of 0.89 (flume) respectively 0.97 (Monash) and a RMSE of 13.4 NTU respectively 12.5 NTU, the models can predict turbidity with high

precision. This was then verified by the performance of the flume model on the test set composed of 4445 samples shown in Figure 19 ($R^2 = 0.87$, $RMSE = 14.5$ NTU). These results are excellent, especially when considering the high variability of samples present in both datasets. In the flume campaign, the wastewater was monitored over 5 months. Many rain events occurred, during which stormwater was mixed with wastewater. Additionally, this catchment is connected to industrial areas, and potential discharge of industrial waste. The Monash campaign contains samples from the inlet of three treatment plants, as well as samples from a stormwater treatment creek. Despite this challenging aspect of the data, both models can estimate turbidity precisely and in a robust way.

a) Flume dataset

b) Monash dataset

turbidity ($R^2 = 0.97$, $RMSE = 12.5$ NTU)

Figure 18: Evaluation of the flume turbidity model (a) and of the Monash turbidity model (b). Both models have similar performances with a RMSE around 13 NTU.

Figure 19: Evaluation of the flume turbidity model (test set). Model performances are only slightly lower than on the training set, with an increase of RMSE of 1.1 NTU, showing the robustness of the model.

The results from the two PLS models highlight the efficacy of hyperspectral imaging for monitoring wastewater turbidity, in line with the results of other scientific publications on the measurement of turbidity or suspended solids with non-contact optical techniques. Agustsson et al. (2014) used a spectrophotometer in reflectance mode to estimate the turbidity of synthetic waters ($R^2 =$

0.96). Mullins et al. (2018) developed an automated system for turbidity measurements at wastewater treatment facilities based on an RGB camera (10% precision). Li et al. (2020) utilized digital images with wavelengths lying between 380 and 780 nm coupled with machine learning estimators to monitor the total suspended solids concentration in lagoon waters ($R^2 = 0.98$). Recently, Preitner et al. (2023) worked with similar samples as Agustsson et al. (2014) but utilized a multispectral camera with active LED illumination ($R^2 = 0.99$). The use of non-contact techniques for turbidity or suspended solids measurement has been raising interest in the last 10 years, with very promising results, potentially paving the way for more effective monitoring of wastewaters.

Discussion: suitability for UDS application. These results are significant because they could enable a measurement of turbidity in UDS. Turbidity is an important quality indicator as it can be used as proxy for suspended solids concentration, as turbidity is caused by the suspended particles that scatter light (Hannouche et al., 2011). Turbidity combined with discharge can also be used as a proxy for concentration of organic carbon (Métadier and Bertrand-Krajewski, 2011). Currently, the monitoring of turbidity in UDS remains challenging as the optical window of the sensor, in contact with the raw wastewater, gets clogged or obstructed by biofilm growth (Gruber et al., 2006). Similarly to flow measurement, that became possible in sewers only after the development of contactless radar technologies (Bertrand-Krajewski et al., 2021), having a camera-based turbidity sensor opens the door for a more systematic implementation in UDS.

The methodologies and analytical techniques employed in our study are not only applicable to turbidity. It can be adapted for monitoring other water quality parameters like organic pollutants, ammonium nitrogen concentrations (see Figure 20), and ammonia levels (publication in preparation). In a similar study, Huang et al. (2022) demonstrated the potential of hyperspectral imaging for monitoring pH, COD, and polyvinyl alcohol of industrial effluents. This adaptability makes hyperspectral imaging a comprehensive tool for wastewater pollution monitoring, offering a significant advancement over traditional methods that require frequent calibration and maintenance. As environmental regulations tighten and the need for real-time monitoring increases, the application of these advanced imaging techniques will become increasingly vital for ensuring water safety and compliance.

Figure 20: Preliminary results for the modelling of ammonium (publication in preparation). Model performances are not as good as UV-vis sensor, but ammonium trend can be detected.

However, there remain questions to be answered before envisaging an implementation in drainage systems, especially regarding the spectral and spatial range of the imager, regarding the cost of the technology and regarding technical implementation in UDS. First, the spectral range is suited for the measurement of turbidity, as particles can be detected in the visible and infrared range. Turbidimeters typically use 860 nm wavelength source. However, for the measurement of soluble compounds such as organic pollutants, using the UV range might be beneficial. Second, hyperspectral imagers remain a costly technology that prevents their implementation on a large scale in UDS. More research is needed to find out whether more affordable multispectral or even red-blue-green (RGB) imagers can be used instead. Finally, as our research focused on lab and flume tests, we did not quantify the impact of in-sewer processes such as level variations, foam or gas emission on the measurement of light reflection. This is relevant because all those processes have to be taken into consideration to enable an accurate measurement using imagers.

Discussion: A potential alternative to the MV.X for future sewer monitoring. Among the promising alternatives to the MV.X hyperspectral camera, we tested the PollutionKeeper camera (Photrack AG, Switzerland), in the framework of WP6.1 research. This device, equipped with a monochromatic UV-vis camera and a custom LED system, measures light reflectance across the UV and visible spectrum. The measurement principle, as described in Preitner et al. (2023), offers potential advantages over the MV.X, particularly due to its lower cost and sensitivity to UV light. These features could enable more precise measurements of dissolved compounds, such as dissolved organic carbon (DOC).

A prototype of the PollutionKeeper camera was installed and operated alongside the ISA spectrometer (see Section 4.4) at the SUDS facility in UDC from May to July 2024. Reference measurements, including ammonium, COD, and turbidity, were measured for the ISA sensor during this period. These data provide a foundation for developing models to estimate these parameters from PollutionKeeper images. Photrack AG is actively working on the development of such models.

3.6. Sensor 6: DischargeKeeper

Sensor description and testing

Introduction. Operation and planning of sewer networks and wastewater treatment plants, as well as compliance assessment, require knowledge of the volumetric flow. Free surface flow measurement is a challenging task, which is commonly done by systems based on ultrasonic and electromagnetic sensors or by using weirs and flumes that affect the flow and require special installations. Wastewater creates a hard environment for sensors that need to be in contact with the fluid. Moreover, some sensors have limitations measuring under low flow conditions, and sedimentation can affect the reliability of the measurements. We tested an image-based non-contact system for volumetric flow monitoring named DischargeKeeper (Photrack AG, Switzerland). The system mainly consists of an IP camera, a processing unit, and a data transition unit. The DischargeKeeper is capable of optically measuring the water height and the surface velocities using a cross-correlation technique. From the surface velocities, the wetted area, and assuming a vertical velocity distribution, the volumetric flow is calculated (Peña-Haro et al.,

2021). The sensor is already commercially exploited in the field of river monitoring, but we have yet to evaluate its performance in UDS.

Method. We tested the DischargeKeeper at two locations. The first one was a sewer at the EAWAG. The second one was at the BENS flume facility in UDC.

First test: Sewer at EAWAG experimental hall. We tested the DischargeKeeper in a sewer located at the EAWAG. We installed the DischargeKeeper inside the manhole, 1.5 meters above the water's surface (Figure 21). The diameter of the sewer is 1000 mm, and the gradient of the sewer upstream of the manhole is 1.6‰ and 1.5‰ downstream. Since the camera had infrared capabilities, it could record when no natural light was present. We used a NivusCS2 cross-correlation sensor as a reference measurement. We positioned it approximately 300 mm above the manhole. An i-3 level sensor (Nivus) placed at the manhole inlet supplemented the discharge measurement.

The DischargeKeeper measures the discharge in a canal using the following steps. Firstly, the DischargeKeeper uses various optical methods to determine the water level, either by observing the liquid's movement or analyzing color or pattern differences at the boundary between the water surface and the sewer wall. Then the surface velocity is calculated using a cross-correlation method. This involves dividing a zone of interest in the camera's field of view into different windows. The method then determines the temporal displacement of the moving patterns for each window. Because the position and orientation of the camera and the geometry of the sewer system are known, the measured displacement field can be converted from the unit pixel per image into a velocity field with the unit meter per second. The velocity field is used to calculate the surface velocity profile in the direction of flow. The mean velocities at each vertical are either calculated using physical models for the vertical velocity profile or estimated using empirically determined correlations between mean velocity and surface velocity. Finally, the discharge is determined by integrating the mean velocities over the channel width (Peña-Haro et al., 2021).

For this series of tests, we compared the maximum surface velocities between the two methods. We extrapolated the maximum surface velocity of the Nivus wedge sensor. We achieved this by applying a logarithmic fit to the Nivus velocity values at three distinct heights. We took the maximum surface velocity of the Surface Structure Image Velocimetry (SSIV) method from the fit of the measured velocities. We calculated correlation coefficients, RMSE, and mean absolute errors for the surface velocity and discharge values to facilitate a quantitative comparison of the data.

Figure 21: Installation of the DischargeKeeper in the trunk sewer at the Eawag hall.

Second tests: BENS-UDC. The second round of tests was performed within the framework of the Co-UDlabs Transnational Access program. The project UDC-01-BENS-Pena was done using the BENS flume test facility managed by UDC, which consists of a 10 m long and 0.9 m wide bench for studying sewer processes using real wastewater in a conventional circular 300 mm PVC pipe and an egg-shaped cross-section pipe (385 mm height, top radius of 110 mm, and a bottom radius of 55 mm). The inflow is regulated by a set of valves, and the slope of the pipes can be set from 0 to 2%. We opened two 0.9-meter top apertures and two holes on each pipe to facilitate the installation of sensors. We installed the DischargeKeeper camera over the medium section to monitor both pipe flows simultaneously (Figure 22). Eight ultrasound distances were installed along the facility for water height measurement and flow rate estimation (sensors over the triangular weir) through a preliminary calibration. We also used a velocity profiler from UB-Flow (Ubertone, France) for reference measurements. We installed it to monitor the central vertical velocity profile of both pipes at the same location as the DischargeKeeper camera. We conducted a total of 53 tests, setting the input flow rate, downstream boundary condition, and slope for various conditions across the facility's full range, including slopes between 0.2 and 1.5%, flows between 1 and 6 L/s, and water depths between 15 and 180 mm.

Figure 22: (left) BENS flume and scheme of the sensors installed in the facility; (right) Processing of a 5-second-long video, the red line shows the optically measured water level and the arrows are the velocity vectors, the lighter colour indicates faster velocities.

Results and discussion

Results. In the Eawag tests, we conducted a 24-hour measurement campaign, performing measurements every 15 seconds (Figure 23). Since both methods measure velocities, we compared velocities instead of discharges to reduce uncertainty. The Nivus and SSIV maximum surface speeds were related with a correlation coefficient of 0.78. The RMSE and mean absolute error were both about 5.5 cm/s, which is an 11.3% difference (Peña-Haro et al., 2019). There are

two possible explanations for this difference. First, the positions where the surface velocities are measured are not identical. Since the manhole is between two sewer pipes with different slopes, velocity may be slower. The Nivus sensor, which is located upstream and measures at a 45° angle, may account for the slightly slower surface velocities measured downstream by the DischargeKeeper. Secondly, it's important to note that both Nivus (which extrapolates the velocity to the surface using a fitting to three data points) and SSIV (where the maximum velocity is not always in the middle of the channel) subject their determination of these maximum surface velocities to certain uncertainties, which may prevent an optimal comparison.

Figure 23: Surface velocity time series DischargeKeeper (red) and NIVUS (green).

In UDC, the camera correctly recorded the videos needed for velocity estimation during the three months of duration of the tests, with no maintenance or re-calibration needed. Depths and surface velocities obtained in the circular pipe from the different instrumentations for the short test ST25 are presented in Figure 24. The videos recorded had to be processed by the sensor's company and no more data was made available to UDC. The possibility of not sharing data openly is a valid exception for SMEs within the Co-UDlabs TA programme. During test ST25, the flow varied while the slope and the downstream boundary condition were kept constant. Water depths resulted in a good fit between devices, but it was not possible to compare flow discharges due to the difficulty of estimating them using surface velocities and depths in sewers. DischargeKeeper was developed and is commercialized for river monitoring, and the hypotheses used increase uncertainty in case of sewers. Regarding velocities (Figure 24), it was not possible to evaluate the accuracy of the sensor since the different nature of the variables measured (mean surface velocity, mean velocity of the central profile, and bulk velocity from flow measurement and depth) was not considered. The results from the Transnational Access project are allowing the SME behind the sensor (Photrack AG) to investigate how different sewer cross-sections and water heights affect the vertical velocity profiles and flow calculation in sewers to adapt the technique from river monitoring to urban drainage systems and obtain through CFD a more accurate transformation from surface velocity to depth-average velocities.

Figure 24: Depth (left) and velocity (right) results obtained from DischargeKeeper, UB-Flow velocity profiler and ultrasound depth sensors for experiment ST25, where flow varies for a certain slope and downstream boundary condition.

Discussion. Tests conducted during the transnational access at the BENS facility (UDC) revealed that further development of the technique is necessary for accurate flow discharge estimation in sewer applications. The data collected during the TA is being used to this purpose by the SME to obtain through CFD a more accurate transformation of surface velocity to depth-average velocities. This development was applied to EAWAG data and compared to cleaned data from the same NIVUS flowmeter data used for the comparison of velocities as described above.

Figure 25: Scatterplot of credible NIVUS data vs. DischargeKeeper CFD-based flow estimates shows that the DK underestimates the flow data in comparison to the operational flow meter, but deviations are <10% in medium and high flows (see Appendix C).

DischargeKeeper tends to underestimate flow, especially at low levels. Its accuracy improves with higher flows: the mean bias drops from -15.6 l/s (-21.4%) at low flow to -8.0 l/s (-6.8%) at high flow. The RMSE also decreases from 18.0 l/s to 11.6 l/s, showing better performance under

high-flow conditions. While the NIVUS meter hasn't been validated with independent tracer tests, the comparison suggests DischargeKeeper works well at medium and high flows. At low flows, larger errors likely come from assumptions about velocity profiles and sensor sensitivity. A scatterplot (Figure 25) supports this, showing good agreement at high flows and underestimation at low flows—possibly due to lower resolution or simplified surface velocity-to-flow conversions, like unsteady hydraulics or changing roughness (see Appendix C for details).

The DischargeKeeper, already successfully used for discharge measurements in natural waters or surface runoff measurement, demonstrates the potential of this image-based method for determining flow discharge at sewers. Importantly, the DischargeKeeper is non-contact, making it low-maintenance, easy to install, and robust—having operated for several months in actual sewers. Its camera-based method also enables visual monitoring, often in real time, adding a valuable layer of situational awareness.

3.7. Sensor 7: Pipe mapping FSB

Sensor description and testing

Introduction. Maps of underground infrastructure are often incomplete or incorrect. This issue arises not only from a lack of appropriate plans and periodic infrastructure monitoring, but also from discrepancies between the as-built and as-designed geometries in design plans. Mapping the actual geometry of underground drainage pipes serves both to have a curated asset inventory and to better simulate hydraulic processes. Nevertheless, reconstructing the geometry of underground infrastructure is costly due to the challenges to access and the substantial length of pipes to manage. At the same time, navigation in underground infrastructure is a challenge. GPS and radio navigation are often hampered by attenuation by the ground and reinforced concrete structures. Other strategies for navigation may rely on optical guidance and reconstruction (for instance, structure from motion) or dead reckoning, where the position is derived from relative motion. Unfortunately, these methods suffer from the accumulation of errors, in which small instantaneous errors in the reconstruction of displacements compound, resulting in large absolute positional errors after some time.

Inertial sensors based on accelerometers and magnetometers have been used for navigation in aerospace, autonomous vehicles, and vessel/submarine applications. Often, these sensors provide an estimate of the current position/velocity/heading, which are periodically corrected using other navigation cues, such as GPS or relative position to reference points. To mitigate the accumulation of errors, highly advanced instrumentation is used (such as optical inertial motion units). However, scaling these implementations to pipe mapping requires low weight, low power, and low cost (i.e., sensors are likely damaged or lost in operations), which often have a significantly lower resolution.

In this sensor testing effort, we aim at ascertaining the degree of applicability of a low-cost acceleration/magnetometer chip to reconstruct pipe geometries based on inertial navigation. We study the time stability and drift of sensors. Additionally, we study the possibilities to supplement the inertial navigation estimates with optical and Lidar-based instrumentation.

Methods. A prototype of a battery-powered, low-cost inertial navigation system was constructed. This consisted of a waterproof enclosure, a microcontroller, a low-cost accelerometer/

magnetometer (FX0S8700), a gyroscope (GXAS21002), a camera, and a time-of-flight Lidar (VL53L1X). Table 5 provides a list of components, characteristics, and estimated price (in 2023 Euro).

Table 5: Components of IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) sensor prototype.

Component	ID	Variables	Characteristics	Approx. cost
IMU	FX0S8700 + FXAS21002	Linear acceleration – Magnetometer (3-axis) Angular rate gyro (3-axis)	Gyro Zero-rate level 0.3906 dps at +/- 250 dps (degree per second)	€ 15.00
Lidar	VL53L1X	Vertical distance		€ 18.00
Camera	RPI WWCAM	Top-view (fish-eye)	5 MP, 160 deg	€ 12.00
Controller	Raspberrypi Zero 2W	Control, communication and synchronization	100 Hz measurement frequency IMUs + Lidar, 5 fps (frame per second) (5 Mpix images)	€ 20.00

We conducted a series of laboratory experiments to: i) characterize the natural drift of the IMU system (i.e., static or quasistatic drift); ii) evaluate the performance of the inertial navigation system, camera, and top-Lidar characteristics within a real section of pipe (15 m with a 90-degree bend) in the laboratory (Figure 26). Table 6 provides a summary of the tests conducted. We sampled the IMU and Lidar at 100 Hz while capturing images at 5 frames per second. We performed the reconstructed positions using Euler integration of the IMU data and Madgwick orientation filtering (Python library AHRS - Attitude and Heading Reference Systems).

Figure 26: A)/B) IMU prototype during the in-pipe testing, C) IMU prototype, D) Control server and user interface

Table 6: Experimental matrix of tests done with the FSB pipe mapping sensor.

Description	Facility (incl. location, matrix)	Description	Duration
Zero drifts & noise when warmed (stability)	Laboratory in different orientations	The sensor is placed at a fixed stable location and all sensors are queried during 15 min. Noise and bias from magnetometer, accelerometer and gyroscopes are extracted.	10 replicates x 15 min
Zero drift & noise when started (restart)	Laboratory in different orientations	The sensor is cooled down during > 5 min. The sensor is placed at a fixed stable location and all sensors are queried during 5 min. Noise and bias from magnetometer, accelerometer and gyroscopes are extracted.	10 replicates x 5 min
Pipe trajectory	15 m PVC pipe with 90 degree bend	The instrument is inserted and hand-pulled with a rope through a 15-meter pipe (horizontally placed) and an L shape. Known starting and ending coordinates. Sensor records IMUs (100 Hz), Lidar (100 Hz) and camera data (5 fps)	4 measurement series

Results and discussion

Results. Table 7 presents the summary statistics of the inertial motion unit data (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer) during time drift under static conditions. This test provides information on the noise and drift suffered by the different variables due to environmental and sensor noise under static conditions. Additionally, four series of measurements were carried out

to reconstruct the inner path of a 15-meter PVC pipe section based on inertial integration. This involved a travel time of approximately 70 seconds, consisting of 12 straight meters and an additional 3 meters after a 90-degree bend.

Figure 27 presents an example of test 2, displaying the time series for the IMU, Lidar, and the synchronization data (A, B, D). Additionally,

Figure 27 (C and E) provides post-processed orientation (Euler angles) and reconstructed position by integrating the IMU data. All pipe tests resulted in drifts of 1000s of meters at the reconstructed coordinate at the end of the pipe.

Table 7: Summary of static IMU stability and restart mean and zero-drift tests.

	Gyrox (dps)	Gyroy (dps)	Gyroz (dps)	Accx (m/s ²)	Accy (m/s ²)	Accz (m/s ²)	Magx (μ T)	Magy (μ T)	Magz (μ T)
Stability measurements (15 min data)									
Mean	0.0146	-0.0019	-0.0136	0.2270	-0.875	10.222	76.871	-8.5257	-312.26

Standard deviation	0.003841	0.003324	0.002428	0.0086	0.0101	0.0130	0.7364	1.0458	1.2831
Zero-drift	0.0006	0.0011	-0.0002	-0.0001	-0.0025	-0.0016	-1.1496	0.5492	1.3269
Restart (5 min data after cooling down)									
Mean	0.010751	-0.00391	-0.01276	0.201935	-1.03209	10.2168	46.91998	-3.41507	-336.034
Standard deviation	0.003876	0.00339	0.002411	0.007907	0.009866	0.01299	0.929012	1.209148	1.765942
Zero-drift	0.001974	0.002572	-0.00063	-0.00105	-0.00077	-0.00514	-2.14801	1.814407	3.98794

Figure 28 shows examples of the top-view camera images from a pipe test. With the current instrumentation (e.g., RPi Zero 2 W microcontroller), we could not go beyond 5 frames per second at 5 Mpix (bandwidth limitation). In order to recover velocimetry estimates from the camera, a sufficiently small displacement should be captured. We conducted these tests at an approximate speed of 0.2 m/s, resulting in interframe displacements of 5 cm. Additionally, there is a trade-off between the required resolution of the image, which defines the minimum features retrieved, the lighting intensity, which results in higher battery consumption but can mitigate motion blur due to camera exposure, and the storage limits of the sensor. For instance, 5 Mpix images at 5 fps generate 13 MB/s of data, requiring in-sensor storage.

Figure 27: Example of data extract from Test P1.2. A) Measurements from IMU (accel, mag, gyro), B) Lidar data, C) Post-processed Euler angles (reconstructed orientation), D) Synchronization of sensors, E) Estimates of velocity and position at the end of the pipe section.

Figure 28: Examples of camera top-view from the pipe tests (5 Mpix, 5 fps).

Conclusions. The current accuracy of low-cost IMUs is likely insufficient to retrieve pipe geometries within realistic pipe lengths and inspection times. According to the static tests, the estimated zero-drift in acceleration was between (0.0001 to 0.005) m/s^2 . The typical expected transport time between inspection access points, such as manhole openings, ranges from approximately 25 to 50 m, while the transport speeds of a passive in-flow element typically range from 0.2 to 0.5 m/s. This leads to positional errors ranging from at least 12 m to 50 m, only accounting for the linear acceleration drift error. When the accumulated errors in the integration of orientation and acceleration during transport are compounded, the error in the integrated position can increase by two orders of magnitude. Using typical integration schemes (i.e., IMU Madgwick filter) to derive position by merging the accelerometer, gyro, and magnetometer in the in-pipe reconstruction resulted in drifts of 100s–1000s of meters for an inspection of 70 seconds within a pipe of 15 meters. Additionally, underground features like active power cables or concrete-reinforced steel armatures can disrupt the magnetometer data, leading to larger reconstruction errors. Therefore, the use of magnetometer fused orientation estimates in real pipe environments should be still properly tested. The use of Lidar altimeters and cameras is likely to allow detecting the position of manhole covers. However, we experienced difficulties finding lens settings for the camera that would both recover sufficient detail from the pipe geometry and not blur due to motion or out-of-focus. The top distances to be resolved by both camera and Lidar are expected to be between 10 cm and 300 cm (i.e., lowest diameter pipeline to top of manhole aperture).

To fully characterize other IMU devices with lower drift and measurement error, further testing is necessary. However, low-cost inertial navigation without the support of visual odometry, sonar, Lidar, or other types of additional data referencing will be very challenging with current low-cost sensor characteristics. The current TRL of this instrumentation is still low: TRL 2-3.

3.8. Sensor 8: Lidar sediment mapping

Sensor description and testing

Objective. Some stormwater management and SUDS facilities contribute to the interception of solids and particulate pollutants transported by runoff, like settling tanks, infiltration trenches, swales, etc. In these facilities, sediments accumulate progressively, and cleansing becomes necessary i) to remove and treat the contaminated sediments, and ii) to recover the storage and infiltration capacity. Monitoring the sediment accumulation in such facilities is usually done manually, at some point locations only. The objective of this tentative sensor test was to evaluate if a Lidar mounted on a drone could be used to obtain sediment maps which could help practitioners to monitor sediment accumulation and to make informed decisions about cleansing.

Sensor description. The Lidar sensor is a Zenmuse L1 from DJI (Shenzen, China). The sensor (Figure 29) is mounted on a drone (Figure 30).

The main characteristics of the Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor are the following ones (more details available at <https://www.dji.com/fr/support/product/zenmuse-l1>):

- Detection range: 450 m at 80% reflectivity, 190 m at 10% reflectivity.

- System accuracy: horizontal: 10 cm at 50 m, vertical: 5 cm at 50 m.
- Ranging accuracy: 3 cm at 100 m
- Point cloud format PNTS / LAS / PLY / PCD / S3MB
- Reconstruction model format B3DM / OSGB / PLY / OBJ / S3MB.

Figure 29: DJI Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor (source: www.gim-international.com)

Figure 30: Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor installed on a drone for testing (photo: R. Poncet, INSA Lyon).

Testing site. The testing of the Zenmuse L1 Lidar sensor was carried out in the Django Reinhardt stormwater infiltration tank, in Chassieu, Lyon, France, on 16 May 2023, by the Air Images Consulting drone company (www.airimagesconsulting.fr). This infiltration tank (Figure 31) has a bottom area of approx. 2.1 ha and a maximum storage volume of 61000 m³. Vegetation has progressively grown on the bottom of the infiltration tank (Figure 32) which was initially made of stones and gravels.

Figure 31: Django Reinhardt stormwater infiltration tank in Chassieu, Lyon, France (boundaries of the infiltration tank in yellow). (source: JLBK from Google Maps).

Figure 32: Vegetation in Django Reinhardt stormwater infiltration tank. Top: in 2015 (source: OTHU; bottom: in May 2023 during the Lidar testing (source: INSA). The growth of the vegetation is noticeable, with many bushes and small trees.

Methods for testing. To evaluate the ability of the Lidar sensor to detect modifications in the relief of the bottom of the tank, two drone flights have been done:

- Flight #1, to be used as reference flight.

- Flight #2, after some solids of various sizes and shapes have been laid at various locations on the bottom of the tank, sometimes in an easily visible position, sometimes partly hidden by or under the vegetation, to simulate changes of the relief aiming to mimic changes of the sediment map.

The solids laid on the bottom of the infiltration tank are listed in Table 8. Some solids are shown in Figure 33. The test then consists in calculating the relief differences between flights 1 and 2, to check if the Lidar data allows detecting and measuring the solids laid between flights 1 and 2.

Table 8: Solids laid on the bottom of the infiltration tank for the Lidar sensor testing.

Solid type	Width (cm)	Length (cm)	Height (cm)	Diameter (cm)	Quantity placed	Comment
Iron cage	24	34.5	23		3	
Jerrican	17	30	24		1	
Brick	10	22	5		4	
Brick block	20	48.5	19		4	
Fine grid	123	76		4	1	4 cm * 4 cm mesh
Wide grid	90	60		5	1	3.5 cm * 3.5 cm mesh
PVC pipe		106		10	1	
MF drain		199		10	1	
MM drain		198		10	1	
Construction cone	28	28	50	4.9	4	
Wooden plank	70	60	1		1	
Tennis ball				6	2	
Plastic balls				6	20	
Ecocup			11.5	5.2 to 7	1	
Concrete test tube			19.6	11	2	
Plexiglas lid			1	30	1	transparent
Jar 1			19.5	21	1	
Jar 2			19.5	21	1	
Jar 3			15.5	17.5	1	
Jar 4			15.5	17.5	1	
Bag of sand					5	25 kg
Bucket of soil					5	

Figure 33: Examples of solids laid on the bottom of the infiltration tank for the Lidar sensor testing.

Results and discussion

Raw Lidar images of flights #1 and #2 are shown respectively in Figure 34 and Figure 35. Bushes and trees are clearly visible, as well as the asphalted ramp providing vehicle access to the bottom of the infiltration tank (visible also on Figure 32 bottom, on the right side). Lidar data files resulting from the experiments were very large (approx. 1.6 GB each) and could not be easily processed on standard laptops due to limited memory and processor capacity. Therefore an external high-

capacity computing server was necessary to i) process data and ii) display and manipulate figures. This is a strong constraint for possible non-specialist users of Lidar data collected over large areas.

As the raw images cover more than 2 ha, they have been split in 10 square sub-images numbered 1 to 10 to facilitate data processing (Figure 36 left). The square nr 6 includes the access ramp where detecting differences between flights #1 and #2 is easier compared to other areas with stones, gravels and vegetation. In particular, the wind was not negligible during the flights, which led to movements of the vegetation, making impossible the detection of the solids laid in vegetated areas.

Figure 34: View of flight #1 Lidar data (figure made with the Matlab Lidar toolbox 24.2).

Figure 35: View of flight #2 Lidar data (figure made with the Matlab Lidar toolbox 24.2).

Figure 36: Lidar images cutting structure.

A sub-area of the square nr 6 (black rectangle in Figure 36 right) has been selected to show example of results in this report, with x coordinates from 852210 to 852240 and y coordinates from 6517040 to 6517060.

After resetting the raw Lidar images to ensure that the same geographical points have the same x and y coordinates for both flights (as the drone made two independent successive flights – this may contribute to degrade a little bit the resolution due to interpolating raw data), the differences between flights #1 and #2 have been calculated for the sub-area. The results are shown in Figure 43, where most values (i.e. differences) are equal or very close to zero (green points on the middle of the colour scale) while random movements of branches and leaves of bushes and trees due to the wind led to values very different from zero (blue and red points).

Figure 37: Lidar image of the difference flight #2 – flight #1.

A zoom on the access ramp (

Figure 38), with rescaled Z axis and colour bar between -0.05 and +0.3 m, allows to observe more details. The concrete block (Figure 39 left), the heap of sand 1 (Figure 39 right) and the heap of sand 2 (Figure 39 middle) are detected.

Figure 38: Lidar image of the difference flight #2 – flight #1 : rescaled zoom on access ramp.

Figure 39: Concrete block (left), heap of sand 2 (middle) and heap of sand 1 (right).

Conclusions. The Lidar allows to detect changes in the topography between the two flights with a resolution of approximately 1-2 cm in altitude. Movements of the vegetation due to the wind prevented to detect changes in vegetated areas. Based on this preliminary test, if used without wind and without vegetation (for example in the winter season or after vegetation trimming), the method may allow to detect sediment accumulation in stormwater tanks provided fixed marks at known level are installed in several points of interest for comparison. However, this method requires i) an external drone service company and ii) the access to a high capacity computing server as the processing of very large data .las files is not possible with laptops.

3.9. Summary of the results and discussion

We used the four main sensor testing criteria defined in section 2.4 to identify trends in the sensors we tested: TRL, quality of testing, operational performance, and technical performance, as summarized in

Table 9. We discuss below each of those points individually.

Table 9: Summary of the sensor evaluations (DK= Discharge Keeper, PM = Pipe Mapping, SM=Sediment Mapping).

	PAH	Proteus	LPICM	ISA	MV.X	DK	PM FSB	Lidar SM
1) TRL	5	5	4	5	4	5	2	5
2) Quality of testing	3	3	5	5	5	5	3	5
3) Operational performance	1	1	5	4	5	4	2	5
4) Technical performance	1	1	5	4	4	4*	3	5
4a) Range	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	4
4b) Accuracy	1	1	5	4	4	4	3	4

*The assessment of the DischargeKeeper device here only considers surface velocities and water levels. For details, e.g. flow considerations, see Section 3.6.

Technological readiness level

We tested a good mix of commercially available sensors (5/8) and technologies in development (3/8). Among the sensors with high technological readiness, two did not demonstrate good technical or operational performance: the PAH sensor and the Proteus sensor. Despite potential for the monitoring of sewer wastewaters, those two sensors did not show a sufficient accuracy or reliability. The remaining three sensors with high TRL, Lidar sediment mapping, DischargeKeeper and ISA, had good to high performances, showing their potential for direct implementation in UDS. Among the sensors with lower TRL, two of them, LPCIM and MV.X, had promising performance and with necessary adaptation, could be implemented in UDS in the future. We classified the MV.X sensor to the lower TRL category despite it being commercially available because the algorithm necessary for data analysis still required improvement. The Pipe Mapping FSB did not perform well in any category.

Quality of testing

We were able to test the sensors in a very extended way for 5/8 sensors. For all of those sensors, we tested them at least in pilot facilities (MV.X, ISA), and even in real world facilities (LPCIM, DischargeKeeper, Lidar sediment mapping). The sensors were tested for an extended period of time (>10 days) and/or in two different locations (ISA, MV.X, Dischargekeeper, LPCIM). We were also able to collect sufficient reference measurements to assess the sensor's performance in a robust way. PAH and Proteus sensors were well evaluated, but only in one location because the first tests were not promising enough to justify further testing.

Operational performance

Assessing operational performance in sewers and raw wastewater at wastewater treatment works (WTWs) is particularly challenging. We prioritized field testing, when possible, but most sensors were tested in pilot-scale facilities. Our evaluation focused on field implementation and maintenance requirements. The PAH and Proteus sensors performed poorly, requiring careful calibration and maintenance. On the opposite, The DischargeKeeper, Lidar Sediment Mapping, and MV.X sensors, which utilize non-contact monitoring principles, stood out for their reliability, operating effectively for several months in raw wastewater without significant issues.

Correlation-based sensors such as ISA and MV.X requires, however, high initial efforts for their calibration before being able to perform in UDS.

Technical performances

The technical performance of two sensors was low (one out of five) for two sensors. For the remaining sensors but one (Pipe Mapping FSB), we measured overall good (4/5) performance, which is promising for future implementation in UDS. Tendentially, the range of the sensor is well suited to the UDS need, and the reported accuracy is middle/good. In the context of quality monitoring in UDS, those results are very promising, as state-of-the-art wastewater monitoring technologies are often performing poorly in the harsh UDS environment.

General discussion

Our study highlights key trends in the performance and applicability of water quality sensors in UDS, offering valuable insights into their strengths and limitations. Sensors targeting specific pollutants often struggle in wastewater and UDS environments due to the inherent complexity and variability of such systems. In contrast, sensors focusing on proxy measurements, such as ISA and LPICM targeting ammonium, demonstrate greater promise. Proxy-based approaches, which leverage correlations between measurable parameters and target pollutants, appear better suited for these applications, underscoring the value of robust calibration and validation processes.

Looking ahead, next-generation sensors should prioritize innovations such as edge processing for real-time data analysis, adaptive monitoring capabilities to switch between dry and wet weather modes, and integration with external data sources like weather radar. Self-diagnostics, exemplified by the emerging “heartbeat” functionality from the Endres and Hauser company, will play a pivotal role in ensuring data quality and reducing maintenance demands. Additionally, incorporating contextual information about sensor deployment locations can further optimize sensor performance and applicability.

These developments, coupled with ongoing advances in technology and system integration, hold significant potential to enhance the effectiveness and reliability of water quality monitoring in urban drainage systems.

4. Data validation with UDMT

The reader must refer to the UDMT User Manual for explanations about the software tool and its use. The user manual is available at this link.⁶

Five data validation tests will be carried out in this example for the data collected with the PAH sensor (see Section 3.2):

- **the physical range:** values within this range are valid (1), otherwise they are not valid (0).
- **the measurement range:** values within this range are valid (1), otherwise they are not doubtful and require manual checking (0.5).

⁶ <https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V>

- **the expert range:** values within this range are valid (1), otherwise they are not doubtful and require manual checking (0.5).
- **the gradient:** values within this range are valid (1), otherwise they are not doubtful and require manual checking (0.5).
- **the relative uncertainty:** values within this range are valid (1), otherwise they are not doubtful and require manual checking (0.5).

Four files are necessary to run the UDMT data validation tests.

Time series file: the time series file PAHDV.csv (Figure 40) contains three columns :

- the time from 30 May 2022 10:12 to 31 Dec. 2022 23:58
- the PAH concentration
- the standard uncertainty of the PAH concentration, set to 12.5 µg/L (half of the total accuracy given as 5 % of full scale according to sensor specifications given by the manufacturer). In practice, the standard uncertainty must be estimated from calibration experiments carried out by the user.

Time	PAH_ug_per_L	uPAH_ug_per_L
29-Nov-2022 05:16:00	15.9958	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:18:00	16.3591	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:20:00	15.3127	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:22:00	17.305	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:24:00	17.2083	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:26:00	17.2306	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:28:00	16.6133	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:30:00	16.8899	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:32:00	16.4885	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:34:00	17.431	12.5
29-Nov-2022 05:36:00	16.8762	12.5

Figure 40: Extract of the PAHDV.csv file.

Test thresholds file: the thresholds file PAHTR.csv (Figure 41) contains the following values:

- the physical range of the sensor: values from MR_Min = 1 to MR_Max = 499 µg/L are considered as valid (to detect extreme values 0 and 500 µg/L and beyond).
- the sensor measuring range: values from PR_Min = 5 to PR_Max = 250 µg/L are considered as valid for this site and this sensor (assumed to be a realistic range in this example).
- the expert range: values from ER_Min = 10 to ER_Max = 150 µg/L are considered as valid for this site and this sensor, according to e.g. previous knowledge (expected range of most frequent values).
- the gradient: gradients below GR_Min = 0.001 µg/L/min (flat signal) or above GR_Max = 20 µg/L/min (abrupt changes) in one time step Dt = 2 min are detected for further analysis before they can be validated.
- the absolute uncertainty: AU = NaN (not applied).

- the relative uncertainty: values with relative standard uncertainty RU higher than 0.25 (i.e. 25%) are considered as not enough reliable for validation.

The above thresholds values are first estimates set only for the UDMT demo application: in real practice, threshold values must be progressively adapted by the user according to his/her expertise to simulate what he/she would do with a manual data validation process.

T	PAH_ug_per_L	uPAH_ug_per_L
PR_Min	1	NaN
PR_Max	499	NaN
MR_Min	5	NaN
MR_Max	250	NaN
ER_Min	10	NaN
ER_Max	150	NaN
GR_Min	0.001	NaN
GR_Max	10	NaN
AU	NaN	NaN
RU	NaN	0.25

Figure 41: PAHTR.csv file.

Redundancy matrix file: not applicable in this example, all values set to zero (Figure 42).

M_R	PAH_ug_per_L	uPAH_ug_per_L
PAH_ug_per_L	0	0
uPAH_ug_per_L	0	0

Figure 42: PAHRM.csv file.

Uncertainty matrix file: not applicable in this example, values set to zero (Figure 43).

M_U	PAH_ug_per_L	uPAH_ug_per_L
PAH_ug_per_L	0	1
uPAH_ug_per_L	0	0

Figure 43: PAHUM.csv file.

After the above four csv files have been uploaded (Figure 44), the application of UDMT leads to the following results (for legibility of the following figures, only the 2-day period from 28-Nov-2022 00:00:00 to 29-Nov-2022 23:58:00 is displayed).

Figure 44: Screenshot of the UDMT just before launching the selected data validation tests.

- Physical range test: values below 1 and above 499 $\mu\text{g/L}$ are rejected (red markers).

Figure 45: UDMT physical range test outcomes.

- Sensor measuring range test: values below 5 and above 250 $\mu\text{g/L}$ are considered as doubtful (yellow markers) because they are not expected in this site with this sensor and require user expertise before final validation or rejection.

Figure 46: UDMT sensor measuring range test outcomes.

- Expert range test: values below 10 and above 150 $\mu\text{g/L}$ are considered as doubtful (yellow markers) because they are not frequently observed (for example only 5% of the measured values), and require user expertise before final validation or rejection.

Figure 47: UDMT expert range test outcomes.

- Gradient test: gradients below 0.001 $\mu\text{g/L/min}$ (flat or almost flat signal) or 20 $\mu\text{g/L/min}$ (abrupt changes) are considered as abnormal (yellow markers) in these monitoring site and conditions and require user expertise before final validation or rejection.

Figure 48: UDMT gradient test outcomes.

- Relative uncertainty test: values with relative standard uncertainty RU higher than 0.25 (i.e. 25%) are considered as doubtful (yellow markers) and require user expertise before final validation or rejection.

Figure 49: UDMT relative uncertainty test outcomes.

Considering globally all applied tests by means of the median grade, the outcomes are shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50: UDMT global validation based on the median grade of all applied tests.

5. Data availability

Table 10: Link to the repositories where data are openly available.⁷

Sensor name	Link to repository
PAH NA	
Proteus NA	
LPICM NA	
ISA	Eawag tests: https://doi.org/10.25678/000D3C
MV.X	Eawag tests: https://doi.org/10.25678/000D3C
DischargeKeeper NA	
PipeMapping NA	
Lidar NA	

6. Contributions to the objectives of the Co-UDlabs project

The activities on smart monitoring and sensor testing in the Co-UDlabs project directly support the project's three main objectives: i) improve cooperation and innovation, ii) facilitate transnational access, and iii) strengthen the services of the research infrastructures (RIs) of the involved partners.

⁷ Data will be made available in early 2025 and this section will be updated accordingly before the end of the Project.

6.1. Objective 1: Fostering cooperation and innovation in Urban Drainage

One key objective of the project is testing new sensors that monitor wastewater and urban drainage systems. In Task 6.1, we evaluated the eight innovative sensors discussed above. This helped identify promising technologies that can improve urban water management (

Table 9).

Although not initially planned, there has been significant collaboration both among RIs and with external partners. Manufacturers have supported sensor installation (e.g., DischargeKeeper, MV.X) and ensured fair data evaluation (ISA, DischargeKeeper). The consistent testing of sensors across multiple sites not only promotes the exchange of best practices and knowledge within the Co-UDlabs team, but it also fosters a more inclusive, transparent, and efficient research environment.

We also found that RIs play a crucial role in driving the transition to smart and sustainable urban drainage management. While monitoring is focusing on hydraulic variables, e.g., water levels and velocities, our selection shows that there is a need for emphasizing water quality and showcasing the benefits of thorough testing.

By making data openly accessible and adhering to standardized testing protocols, the project aligns with the European Open Science Cloud. Efforts are underway to develop data standardization, validation, and interoperability protocols that comply with FAIR principles. Another important aspect is standardizing the data collected by the sensors. Testing includes developing consistent methods for validating sensor data, e.g., with the UDMT, ensuring the information is reliable and compatible with other systems. This supports the urban drainage community by creating uniform standards for data and technology use, making it easier for different systems to work together.

6.2. Objective 2: Facilitating Transnational Access to Research Facilities

Despite not being a direct goal of Task 6.1, which is directly associated with the Joint Research Activities (JRA), the sensor testing activities have created valuable synergies with Transnational Access (TA) initiatives. Through collaboration with enterprises like Photrack AG (DischargeKeeper sensor) and Headwall Photonics (MV.X sensor), sensor testing has extended beyond the TA group. This contributes to facilitating Transnational Access, because these companies are actively involved in joint testing efforts, including contributing to scientific publications. This collaboration plays a key role in the development and validation of new technologies, ensuring they undergo full-scale testing before broader implementation in the water sector. Additionally, Co-UDlabs helps bridge the gap between lab and field testing by supporting the transition of technologies from controlled laboratory environments to real-world urban drainage systems.

6.3. Objective 3: Strengthening services of RIs at the European level through Joint Research Activities

The sensor testing activities in Co-UDlabs significantly contribute to stronger services through joint research activities by improving the understanding of urban drainage systems and supporting data-driven decision-making.

One of the key contributions is the improved understanding of asset deterioration in urban drainage systems. The evaluation of sensors like the Pipe Mapping FSB helps assessing the condition of drainage infrastructure, providing valuable insights into the deterioration processes. These findings can guide strategies for network renewal, renovation, and repair, ultimately enhancing the long-term resilience and sustainability of urban drainage systems.

Additionally, the testing of sensors such as the LPICM, the ISA, and the non-contact MV.X supports the development of more robust and autonomous monitoring techniques. These sensors enable continuous, real-time data collection, improving both the quality and quantity of information available for understanding urban drainage processes. This, in turn, enhances decision-making by providing reliable data that can inform more effective management strategies.

Finally, Co-UDlabs plays a crucial role in evaluating the performance of emerging urban drainage technologies, such as Sustainable Drainage Systems (SuDS) and real-time control systems. Sensor testing is essential for assessing the hydraulic and water quality performance of these technologies, e.g., through novel camera-based sensors that are virtually maintenance-free. By using standardized methods to assess these technologies, e.g., the UDMT, the results from this report provide critical data that helps quantify the suitability of new technology, ensuring it can meet future urban water management needs.

7. Conclusions

In this work, we tested and evaluated eight innovative sensor systems with the potential to advance the management of urban drainage systems, from continuous monitoring of bathing water quality to non-contact pollution monitoring with hyperspectral cameras and novel pipe mapping technology. By fostering collaboration across 5 research institutions and several small and medium enterprises, the project has contributed to the development of new technologies, the sharing of knowledge, and the improvement of monitoring techniques in urban drainage systems.

Key conclusions from our research activities include the recognition that the monitoring of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) is still underdeveloped, particularly in terms of water quality information, which could help quantify the impact and risk of management options.

First, collaboration within the activities in Task 6.1 has been central to its success. Through shared expertise, the project has facilitated the identification of emerging technologies and promoted the exchange of best practices across the urban drainage community. The rigorous testing methodology, which included laboratory, pilot-scale, and full-scale testing, provided valuable insights into sensor performance under a variety of conditions. The selection process for sensors was particularly successful, with a realistic and robust evaluation that ideally involved several months of testing in real sewer systems and challenging wastewater environments.

Second, the development of an evaluation framework based on both quantitative and qualitative indicators has provided a standardized approach for assessing the suitability of emerging sensors. While some attributes require subjective scoring, the framework offers a practical method for filtering out unsuitable sensors and providing a first step in sensor evaluation. The developed tool for data validation, UDMT, not only assesses individual measurements but also tackles data validation and contextualization, emphasizing the significance of comprehending data uncertainty.

Third, our testing identified several promising technologies, such as the LPICM, ISA, the DischargeKeeper, and MV.X sensors, which demonstrated strong potential for implementation in urban drainage systems. These sensors offer significant advantages, including low-power consumption and continuous and non-contact water quality monitoring capabilities. However, not all tested sensors have reached the required technological readiness level yet; some lack ATEX versions or exhibit accuracy limitations, indicating areas that require further research and development.

Looking ahead, mitigating climate change requires improved water quality monitoring and high-quality data for sound decision-making, and digital solutions like UDMT are essential tools for this purpose. Task 6.1 underscored the significance of conducting comprehensive testing when integrating sensors from various fields into urban drainage systems, such as the MV.X, to ensure their effectiveness. Finally, funding programs like transnational access play a crucial role in advancing research and providing the resources needed for continued innovation.

References

- Aerts, R., & Blumensaat, F. (2021). Wie bewerte ich die Leistung von Entwässerungssystemen? Zu Herausforderungen emissionsbasierter Optimierungsstrategien. *Aqua & Gas*, 10(1).
- Agustsson, J., Akermann, O., Barry, D., & Rossi, L. (2014). Non-contact assessment of COD and turbidity concentrations in water using diffuse reflectance UV-Vis spectroscopy. *Environmental Science. Processes & Impacts*, 16(8), 1897–1902. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c3em00707c>
- Becouze-Lareure, C., Dembélé, A., Coquery, M., Cren-Olivé, C., & Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L. (2019). Assessment of 34 dissolved and particulate organic and metallic micropollutants discharged at the outlet of two contrasted urban catchments. *Science of The Total Environment*, 651, 1810–1818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.042>
- Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., Clemens-Meyer, F., & Lepot, M. (Eds.). (2021). *Metrology in Urban Drainage and Stormwater Management: Plug and Pray*. IWA Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.2166/9781789060119>
- Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., Lepot, M. (2023). *UDMT - Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox User Manual version 2023b5*. INSA Lyon. [https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V#returl=https%3A//u.pcloud.link/publink/show%3Fcode%3DkZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V&page=login \(consulted on 13 Nov. 2024\)](https://u.pcloud.link/publink/show?code=kZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V#returl=https%3A//u.pcloud.link/publink/show%3Fcode%3DkZegnQVZM53qyjRJ4cHn7Pi5WzrR9HJ0PL4V&page=login%20(consulted%20on%2013%20Nov.%202024))
- Blumensaat, F. (2020, September 29). *Wie stark verschmutzt ist Mischabwasser wirklich?* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C5YI-GQFCW8>
- Bressy, A., Boutin, G., Benrezkallah, Z., Dubois, P., & Bonhomme, C. (2014). *How to continuously monitor PAHs in urban stormwater using in situ UV fluorescence technology?* 2517824. <https://enpc.hal.science/hal-01068218>
- Brito, R. S., Pinheiro, H. M., Ferreira, F., Matos, J. S., & Lourenço, N. D. (2014). In situ UV-Vis spectroscopy to estimate COD and TSS in wastewater drainage systems. *Urban Water Journal*, 11(4), 261–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2013.783087>
- Chawla, I., Karthikeyan, L., & Mishra, A. K. (2020). A review of remote sensing applications for water security: Quantity, quality, and extremes. *Journal of Hydrology*, 585, 124826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2020.124826>
- Chen, G., Qiao, Y., Zhang, X., Liu, F., Liao, H., Zhang, R., Dong, J., & Tao, B. (2019). Identification and Characterization of Herbicide Penoxsulam Transformation Products in Aqueous Media by UPLC-QTOF-MS. *Bulletin of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, 102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00128-019-02612-2>
- EC. (2017). *Horizon 2020—Work Programme 2018-2020. General Annexes G. Technological readiness levels (TLR)*. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2018-2020/annexes/h2020-wp1820-annex-g-trL_en.pdf
- EC. (2024, October 16). *Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast)*. EC. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/PE-85-2024-INIT/en/pdf>
- Elgarahy, A. M., Eloffy, M. G., Saber, A. N., Abouzid, M., Rashad, E., Ghorab, M. A., El-Sherif, D. M., & Elwakeel, K. Z. (2024). Exploring the sources, occurrence, transformation, toxicity, monitoring, and remediation strategies of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances: A review. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 196(12), 1209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-024-13334-2>
- Grab, T., & Barbisch, L. (2018). *Magnetisch-induktive Leitfähigkeitsmessung* [BSc thesis]. HSR/OST.

- Gruber, G., Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., Beneditis, J. D., Hochedlinger, M., & Lettl, W. (2006). Practical aspects, experiences and strategies by using UV/VIS sensors for long-term sewer monitoring. *Water Practice and Technology*, 1(1), wpt2006020. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2006.020>
- Hannouche, A., Chebbo, G., Ruban, G., Tassin, B., Lemaire, B. J., & Joannis, C. (2011). Relationship between turbidity and total suspended solids concentration within a combined sewer system. *Water Science and Technology*, 64(12), 2445–2452. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.779>
- Heller, S. (2023). *Online Measurements In The Sewer Network* [BSc thesis]. ETH.
- Herngren, L., Goonetilleke, A., Ayoko, G. A., & Mostert, M. M. M. (2010). Distribution of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in urban stormwater in Queensland, Australia. *Environmental Pollution*, 158(9), 2848–2856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2010.06.015>
- Huang, D., Ye, J., Yu, S., Tian, Y., Wen, X., Wang, Y., Ren, L., & Chen, X. (2022). Study on a fast non-contact detection method for key parameters of refractory organic wastewater treatment. *Biochemical Engineering Journal*, 177, 108269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2021.108269>
- Kaplan, G., Yalcinkaya, F., Altıok, E., Pietrelli, A., Nastro, R. A., Lovecchio, N., Ieropoulos, I. A., & Tsipa, A. (2024). The role of remote sensing in the evolution of water pollution detection and monitoring: A comprehensive review. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, 136, 103712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2024.103712>
- Lechevallier, P., Gruber, G., Bareš, V., Neuenhofer, N., Waldner, L., Mahajan, A., Mutzner, L., & Rieckermann, J. (2024a). *Open dataset on wastewater quality monitoring with adsorption and reflectance spectrophotometry in the UV-vis range*. OSF. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/y4pnm>
- Lechevallier, P., Villez, K., Felsheim, C., & Rieckermann, J. (2024b). Towards non-contact pollution monitoring in sewers with hyperspectral imaging. *Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EW00541K>
- Lepot, M., Torres, A., Hofer, T., Caradot, N., Gruber, G., Aubin, J., & Bertrand-Krajewski, J. (2016). Calibration of UV/Vis spectrophotometers: A review and comparison of different methods to estimate TSS and total and dissolved COD concentrations in sewers, WWTPs and rivers. *Water Research*, 101, 519–534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2016.05.070>
- Li, Y., Wang, X., Zhao, Z., Han, S., & Liu, Z. (2020). Lagoon water quality monitoring based on digital image analysis and machine learning estimators. *Water Research*, 172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.115471>
- Métadier, M., & Bertrand-Krajewski, J. L. (2011). Assessing dry weather flow contribution in TSS and COD storm events loads in combined sewer systems. *Water Science and Technology*, 63(12), 2983–2991. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2011.185>
- Mullins, D., Coburn, D., Hannon, L., Jones, E., Clifford, E., & Glavin, M. (2018). A novel image processing-based system for turbidity measurement in domestic and industrial wastewater. *Water Science*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2018.030>
- Obenaus, F., Rosenwinkel, K.-H., Alex, J., Tschepetzki, R., & Jumar, U. (1999). Components of a model-based operation system for wastewater treatment plants. *Water Science and Technology*, 39(4), 103–111. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.1999.0195>
- Pacheco, M., Knutz, T., & Barjenbruch, M. (2020). Multi-Parameter calibration of a UV/Vis spectrometer for online monitoring of sewer systems. *Water Science and Technology*, 82. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2020.398>
- Peña-Haro, S., Carrel, M., Lüthi, B., Hansen, I., & Lukes, R. (2021). Robust Image-Based Streamflow Measurements for Real-Time Continuous Monitoring. *Frontiers in Water*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frwa.2021.766918>

- Peña-Haro, S., Carrel, M., Lüthi, B., Wang, L., Dicht, S., & Leitão, J. P. (2019). Abflussmessungen mittels Videos. Einsatz von Webcams und Smartphones. *Aqua & Gas*, 42–45.
- Preitner, K., Blanc, S., Honzátko, D., Kündig, C., Pad, P., Saeedi, S., Peña-Haro, S., Lechevallier, P., Rieckermann, J., & Dunbar, L. A. (2023, March 15). *Intelligent multispectral vision system for contactless water quality monitoring for wastewater*. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2649921>
- Razguliaev, N., Flanagan, K., Muthanna, T., & Viklander, M. (2024). Urban stormwater quality: A review of methods for continuous field monitoring. *Water Research*, 249, 120929. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120929>
- Rieckermann, J. (2022). *D6.1. Report on review and selection of new/ emerging monitoring technologies to be tested in T6.1.2*. <https://zenodo.org/records/7261618>
- Rieckermann, J., Bloem, S., Ebi, C., Meyer, G., Keel, G., & Blumensaat, F. (2025). A Novel Low-Power Inductive Conductivity Monitor for Continuous Wastewater Quality Monitoring in Sewers. *In Preparation*.
- Sartory, D. P., & Howard, L. (1992). A medium detecting β -glucuronidase for the simultaneous membrane filtration enumeration of *Escherichia coli* and coliforms from drinking water. *Letters in Applied Microbiology*, 15(6), 273–276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-765X.1992.tb00782.x>
- Schilperoort, R. P. S., Gruber, G., Flamink, C. M. L., Clemens, F. H. L. R., & van der Graaf, J. H. J. M. (2006). Temperature and conductivity as control parameters for pollution-based real-time control. *Water Science and Technology*, 54. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2006.744>
- Suslovaite, V. (2023). *Development of a risk based approach to surface water abstraction* [Phd, University of Sheffield]. <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/34483/>
- The standing Committee of Analysts. (2016). *Part 4 Methods for the isolation and enumeration of coliform bacteria and Escherichia coli (including E.coli O157:H7)*.
- Wiest, L. (2023). *Personal communication* [Personal communication].

Appendix A: sensor testing sheets for each sensor

Proteus		
<u>General information</u>		
Sensor name	Proteus	
Model		
measured parameter	E.coli	
Manufacturer	RS Instruments	
Sensing principle	fluorescence/tryptophan	
TLR		5
Link	https://www.rshydro.co.uk/water-quality-monitoring-equipment/water-quality-testing-equipment/multiparameter-water-quality-sonde/proteus-bod-multiparameter-water-quality-meter/	
<u>Manufacturer information</u>		
Range	> 1 CFU/100ml	
Accuracy	±10 Coliforms	
<u>Testing information</u>		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		3
Tested in	Field	
Testing duration	4 weather events (multiple days)	
Number of reference measurements		162
<u>Technical performance</u>		
Overall technical performance		1
Tested range	up to 42000 CFU/100ml	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		4
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	> 5800 during validation	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		1
Data completeness (%)	n/a	
Drifts	n/a	
<u>Operational performance</u>		
Overall operational performance		1
Ease of calibration		2
Frequency of calibration required		2
Ease of maintenance		2
Frequency of maintenance required		3
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		5
ATEX	No (not specified)	

PAH Probe		
General information		
Sensor name	EnviroFlu-HC	
Model	HC-500	
measured parameter	PAHs	
Manufacturer	TriOS	
Sensing principle	UV fluorescence	
TLR		5
Link	https://www.trios.de/en/enviroflu.html	
Manufacturer information		
Range	0-500 ppb PAH	
Accuracy		25% of full scale
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		3
Tested in	lab / field	
Testing duration		217
Number of reference measurements		9
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance		1
Tested range	0-500	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	26.6	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		1
Data completeness (%)		1
Drifts	not evaluated	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance		1
Ease of calibration		1
Frequency of calibration required		5
Ease of maintenance		4
Frequency of maintenance required		2
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		1
ATEX	no	

LPICM		
General information		
Sensor name	Low-Power Inductive Conductivity Monitor (LPICM)	
Model	in-house development	
measured parameter	Electrical Conductivity/Temperature	
Manufacturer	Eawag, ZHAW (prototype)	
Sensing principle	Electromagnetic induction	
TLR		4 custom build based on commercial components, no ATEX certification
Link	https://www.eawag.ch/en/about-us/working/researchenvironment/sensor-lab/	
Manufacturer information		
Range	0-2000 mScm-1	based on sensor InPro®7250 Series, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland
Accuracy	+ - 0.25% of value + 25/μS	Grab and Barbisch (2018), Info sheet of sensor
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		5
Tested in	Lab, Pilot, 3 full-scale sewer systems	<u>test performed in collaboration with utilities and regulators, maintenance by operator</u>
Testing duration	>1000	
Number of reference measurements		26 varies from study to study, difficult to say, 26 with two different instruments for dilution test in the lab
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance		5
Tested range	0-3500 uScm-1	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	15 uS cm-1	<5%
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		5
Data completeness (%)	80-90%	From the sensor it is mainly air inside the clogging protection or too high speed (air on the inside) that leads to erroneous data (less conductivity than reality).
Drifts	no	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance		5
Ease of calibration		5
Frequency of calibration required		5
Ease of maintenance		5
Frequency of maintenance required		5
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		2 power consumption is good 2years runtime at 15min data collection interval
ATEX	no	InPro®7250 Series "HT" would be ATEX certified, we used the ST version

ISA (UDC tests)		
General information		
Sensor name	ISA Spectrometer	
Model	ISA/BlueScan TS	
measured parameter	Absorbance (NH4-N)	We used data-driven modelling to estimate NH4-N from absorbance
Manufacturer	GO Systemelektronik GmbH	
Sensing principle	Spectrometer	
TLR		5
Link	https://www.go-sys.de/en/products/uv-vis-spectrometers/isa-uv-vis-spectrometer-system/	
Manufacturer information		
Range	n/a	
Accuracy	n/a	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		5
Tested in	flume	
Testing duration		31
Number of reference measurements		64
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	4	
Tested range	0-61,7 mg/L	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	4,7 mg/L	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		4
Data completeness (%)	100%	
Drifts	no	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance	4	
Ease of calibration		3 Needs continuous recalibration
Frequency of calibration required		2
Ease of maintenance		4
Frequency of maintenance required		3 Needs continuous maintenance
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		3
ATEX	yes	

ISA (Eawag tests)		
General information		
Sensor name	ISA Spectrometer	
Model	ISA	
measured parameter	Absorbance (NH4-N)	We used data-driven modelling to estimate NH4-N from absorbance
Manufacturer	GO Systemelektronik GmbH	
Sensing principle	UV-vis spectrophotometry	
TLR		5
Link	https://www.go-sys.de/en/products/uv-vis-spectrometers/isa-uv-vis-spectrometer-system/	
Manufacturer information		
Range	n/a	
Accuracy	n/a	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		5
Tested in	pilot	
Testing duration		172
Number of reference measurements		483
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	4	
Tested range	0-61,7 mg/L	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	5,3 mg/L	measured on 433 test samples after data-driven model training with 50 other samples
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		4
Data completeness (%)	98%	
Drifts	no	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance	4	
Ease of calibration		230 min, DI water, equipment, skilled technician
Frequency of calibration required		4 monthly/every 2 months
Ease of maintenance		4 Weekly cleaning with water jet, eventual ethanol
Frequency of maintenance required		3 Weekly / every two weeks
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		3 sensor design (shape, size) not suited for UDS application due to clogging potential
ATEX	yes	

MV.X		
General information		
Sensor name	MV.X hyperspectral imaging system	
Model	MV.X VNIR	
measured parameter	Reflectance (turbidity)	We used data-driven modelling to estimate turbidity from reflectance
Manufacturer	Headwall Photonics (USA)	
Sensing principle	VNIR spectrophotometry	
TLR	4	
Link	https://headwallphotonics.com/products/mac-hine-vision/mv-x-vnir-hyperspectral-imaging-system/	
Manufacturer information		
Range	n/a	
Accuracy	n/a	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing	5	
Tested in	Pilot	
Testing duration		172
Number of reference measurements		4645
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	4	
Tested range	23-280 NTU	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	14.5 NTU	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		4
Data completeness (%)		0,975
Drifts	no	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance	5	
Ease of calibration		5
Frequency of calibration required		5
Ease of maintenance		5
Frequency of maintenance required		5
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		2 power consumption, requires powerful light, line scan, price
ATEX	yes	

DischargeKeeper (UDC tests)		
General information		
Sensor name	DischargeKeeper	
Model		
measured parameter	Water flow from surface velocity and water depth	
Manufacturer	Photrack	
Sensing principle	Image-based	
TLR	5	Exploited commercially for river monitoring
Link	https://www.photrack.ch/dischargekeeper.html	
Manufacturer information		
Range	0.2 - 15 m/s	
Accuracy	n/a	
Flow velocity	0,05	
Water level	1 cm	
Discharge	10%	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing	2	Only water levels were able to be compared.
Tested in	BENS facility (flume with real wastewater)	Part of transnational Access UDC-01-BENS-Pena
Testing duration	90 (1)	Tested 90 days, only one day analysed
Number of reference measurements	6	
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	2	The sensor shown good performance with water depths, but it was not possible to estimate water flow because the model need further development for estimation of flows in sewers.
Tested range	0-5 L/s, 80-120 mm	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need	3	
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	4 mm	Comparison was only possible for water levels
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need	4	For water llevels
Data completeness (%)	n/a	not enough data to evaluate
Drifts	no	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance	4	Few problems when accidentally moved the camera, need manufacturer for data processing.
Ease of calibration	5	Only during installation
Frequency of calibration required	5	Not needed
Ease of maintenance	5	Non-contact device, monthly cleaning of lenses
Frequency of maintenance required	5	Monthly cleaning of lenses
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)	4	Easy to install and low maintenance.
ATEX	no	

DischargeKeeper (Eawag tests)		
General information		
Sensor name	DischargeKeeper	
Model		
measured parameter	Water flow from surface velocity and water depth	
Manufacturer	Photrack	
Sensing principle	Image-based	
TLR	5	
Link	https://www.photrack.ch/dischargekeeper.html	
Manufacturer information		
Range	From pipes to rivers, open channel flows	
Accuracy	n/a	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		5 more than a year installed in a real sewer system
Tested in	pilot sewer (trunk sewer, real wastewater)	
Testing duration	400	days
Number of reference measurements	>1000	parallel installation of NIVUS wedge sensor, reference data available for one day
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	4	The sensor shown good performance with surface velocity estimation, 4 videos analysed
Tested range	0-1 m/s (surface velocity)	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		5
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	Velocity: 11%, 0.055 ms ⁻¹ ; Flow: 17.1%	Comparison to operational flow meter, overall underestimation of 14%. DischargeKeeper is probably most accurate at high flows and errors increase notably under low flow conditions given the current flow estimation.
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		4
Data completeness (%)		5
Drifts	no	lens cleaning might be needed, depending on conditions on monitoring site
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance		5 Sensor was operated in sewers during several months. Issues with lens fogging were encountered, but solved with heated cases
Ease of calibration		3 Only during installation
Frequency of calibration required		4 Once the reference frame is known, No calibration is needed
Ease of maintenance		5 Non-contact device, monthly cleaning of lenses
Frequency of maintenance required		4 Monthly cleaning of lenses
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		5 Easy to install and low maintenance.
ATEX	no	The tested version was not ATEX, but such cameras are available

Pipe Mapping FSB		
General information		
Sensor name	FSB_pipemapping	
Model	Tailored built prototype	
measured parameter	Drift in inertial navigation system for position estimation in underground pipes.	
Manufacturer	NA	
Sensing principle	Measurement of acceleration, angular rate and magnetic field, top-view distance from LIDAR and top-view image from a mounted camera in a passive drifter.	
TLR	2	
Link	n/a	
Manufacturer information		
Range	Accel: 39,2 m/s ² , Mag: 1200 uT, Gyro: 39,2 rad/s, Lidar: 0,4 m	
Accuracy	Accel: std 0,015 m/s ² , Mag: std 1,5 uT, Gyro: std 0,004 rad/s, Lidar: 1% (from manufacturer, under static conditions)	
Testing information		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		3
Tested in	lab/pilot	
Testing duration	5	
Number of reference measurements		24
Technical performance		
Overall technical performance	2	
Tested range	Static tests duration (300-900) seconds. Pipe test duration 70 seconds, length 15 meters.	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need	Expected durations 300 seconds. Expected length (25-50) meters.	
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	Drift of 100s - 1000s meters in positional accuracy after 70 seconds (pilot test).	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need	Drift lower than 10 m.	
Data completeness (%)	n/a	
Drifts	n/a	
Operational performance		
Overall operational performance	2	
Ease of calibration	3	
Frequency of calibration required	5	
Ease of maintenance	4	
Frequency of maintenance required	n/a	
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)	2	
ATEX	no	

Lidar Sediment Mapping		
<u>General information</u>		
Sensor name	Lidar	
Model	Zenmuse L1	
measured parameter	Distances, angles	
Manufacturer	DJI	
Sensing principle	time of travel of light pulse	
TLR		5
Link	https://www.dji.com/fr/support/product/zenmuse-l1	
<u>Manufacturer information</u>		
Range	0 - 450 m	
Accuracy	5 to 10 cm	
<u>Testing information</u>		
Overall quality / reliability of testing		5
Tested in	field	
Testing duration		1
Number of reference measurements	none	
<u>Technical performance</u>		
Overall technical performance		5
Tested range	0-50 m	
Suitability of the range compared to UDS need		4
Tested accuracy (RMSE)	not relevant	
Suitability of the accuracy compared to UDS need		4
Data completeness (%)		100
Drifts	no	
<u>Operational performance</u>		
Overall operational performance		5
Ease of calibration		5
Frequency of calibration required		5
Ease of maintenance		1
Frequency of maintenance required		4
Suitability for UDS application (ATEX, etc.)		4
ATEX	no	

Appendix B: Detailed report on the PAH sensor testing

B.1. Sensor description

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) form a group of organic molecules frequently detected and quantified in stormwater runoff at levels ranging from ng/L to µg/L depending on the molecule (e.g. Becouze *et al.*, 2019). They are mainly produced by incomplete combustion and pyrolysis of petroleum products (gasoline, oil, fuel, etc.), wood, garbage, etc. In urbanized areas, they are linked to traffic and heating. Some PAHs are carcinogenic substances. Usually, only a limited number of PAHs are measured in stormwater, according to pre-established lists like the US EPA list of 16 molecules published in 1976 (Keith, 2014) or the European list of 15 molecules published in 2005 (Wenzl *et al.*, 2006). The following molecules are among the most abundant ones in stormwater runoff: fluoranthene, pyrene, benzo(b)fluoranthene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, benzo-g,h,i-perylene and indenopyrene (Becouze *et al.*, 2019).

PAHs are measured in samples by means of laboratory analytical methods based on GC-MS (gas chromatography – mass spectrometry) or LC-MS/MS (liquid chromatography – double mass spectrometry). Sampling and analyses are costly, and do not allow a continuous online monitoring of PAHs concentrations in stormwater. A PAHs sensor that could be used *in situ* and online could be a very attractive alternative.

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC (Figure B51) has been identified as a potentially interesting sensor to measure PAHs in stormwater. It estimates concentrations of PAHs in the range 0-500 ppb (or µg/L) by means of fluorescence. A xenon lamp light source illuminates the water volume near the probe at 254 nm and the backscattered fluorescence is measured by a photodiode at 360 nm. The estimated concentration is then converted into a 4-20 mA analogic signal. The manufacturer indicates the probe can be used in drinking water, wastewater, airports, refineries, etc. with the following specifications: detection limit 0.3 ppb, measurement accuracy ± 5% of full scale, reproducibility ≤ 0.5% of full scale, response time ≤ 10 s, measurement interval ≥ 5 s, no turbidity compensation.⁸

Figure B51: Trios EnviroFlu-HC 500 probe (source: Trios company website).

B.2. Testing site

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor was tested in the monitoring flume of the Chassieu catchment in Lyon, France. The Chassieu catchment (Figure B52 left) is a 185 ha industrial area in the eastern suburbs of Lyon (45°44'10.30"N/4°57'31.27"E) drained by a separate stormwater sewer system. The catchment mean slope is 0.4 % and its active area is 54 ha. The stormwater runoff is discharged into a detention and settling basin and then into an infiltration basin which recharges

⁸ The complete sensor data sheet is available at: <https://www.trios.de/en/enviroflu.html> (consulted on November 6, 2024).

the groundwater table. The catchment outlet is equipped and monitored as part of the Field Observatory on Urban Hydrology (OTHU) since 2003.⁹

At the catchment outlet (Figure B52 right), a set of sensors allows continuous monitoring (with a 2 min time step) of water depth and flow velocity. A peristaltic pump continuously feeds at approx. 0.7 L/s a monitoring flume in a shelter (Figure B53 right) located above the outlet sewer (Figure B52 right) with water circulating in the sewer during storm events (there is also a small and intermittent dry weather flow in the sewer due to industrial cooling activities in the catchment). Water quality parameters (pH, conductivity, turbidity, temperature) are measured (with a 2 min time step) with online sensors in the monitoring flume (Figure B53 right). Automatic samplers are also installed in the shelter to collect samples at defined time or volume intervals.

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor was installed in the Chassieu monitoring flume for testing (Figure B54 left), where some accidental hydrocarbons spills are occasionally observed (Figure B54 right), in addition to the systematic presence of PAHs during storm events (Becouze *et al.*, 2019).

Figure B52: Left: aerial view of the Chassieu catchment (source: JLBK); right: monitoring shelter at catchment outlet (source: OTHU).

Figure B53: Left: scheme of the shelter equipment (source: JLBK); right: monitoring flume with sensors in the shelter (source: Nicolas Walcker).

⁹ More information online at: www.othu.org.

Figure B54: Left: the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor at the end of testing in the Chassieu monitoring flume (source: Nicolas Walcker); right: accidental spill of hydrocarbons at the outlet of the Chassieu catchment (source: Nicolas Walcker).

B.3. Methods for sensor testing

The sensor testing included two parts: 1) laboratory correlation and 2) *in situ* continuous data collection.

B.3.1. Laboratory correlation

The laboratory test aimed to compare i) the concentration values delivered by the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor immersed in samples collected in Chassieu during storm events, with ii) the PAHs concentrations of the same samples measured by the external accredited Carso laboratory.

The samples have been collected in the monitoring flume by means of the refrigerated auto sampler installed in the Chassieu shelter. Sampling campaigns were decided according to weather forecasts: 1 L samples were taken in glass bottles volume proportionally for each 130 m³ cumulated volume discharged at the catchment outlet. To avoid either contamination or internal changes in the water matrix, the protocol paid attention to carefully respect the cold chain and clean all the glassware (each element was cleaned with TFD4 solvent, tap water and acetone not earlier than 7 days prior to rain events).

Once the samples were grabbed, 240 measurements were recorded immediately on site, with the same data acquisition system as the one running 24/7 in the shelter. Samples were then transported to the laboratory and half of the volume was filtrated with a 0.45 µm paper filter to get latter analyses on both total (T) and dissolved (D) PAH concentrations. Finally, raw and filtrated samples were sent to Carso laboratory and analysed according to their method M_ET283 (gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry), delivering concentrations of 30 PAH molecules with limits of quantification varying from 0.005 to 0.05 µg/L (Table B11), i.e. from 0.001 to 0.01 % of the Trios EnviroFlu-HC full scale.

Table B11: List of the 30 PAH molecules measured by Carso laboratory in total sample (T) and dissolved fraction (D) of the collected samples.

ID nr.	PAH molecule	LoQ (µg/L)	ID nr.	PAH molecule	LoQ (µg/L)
1	2-methyl fluoranthene	0.005	16	Fluorene*	0.005
2	1-methyl naphtalene	0.005	17	Naphtalene*	0.02
3	2-methyl naphtalene	0.02	18	Pyrene*	0.005
4	Acenaphtene*	0.005	19	Phenanthrene*	0.02
5	Acenaphthylene*	0.01	20	Anthraquinone	0.05
6	Anthracene*	0.005	21	Benzo (j) fluoranthene	0.005
7	Benzo (a) anthracene*	0.005	22	Benzo (e) pyrene	0.005
8	Benzo (b) fluoranthene*	0.005	23	Coronene	0.05
9	Benzo (k) fluoranthene*	0.005	24	Dibenzo (a,e) pyrene	0.05
10	Benzo (a) pyrene*	0.005	25	Dibenzo (a,i) pyrene	0.05
11	Benzo (g,h,i) perylene*	0.005	26	Dibenzo (a,h) pyrene	0.05
12	Indeno (1,2,3 cd) pyrene*	0.005	27	Dibenzo (a,l) pyrene	0.05
13	Chrysene*	0.005	28	Dekalin (decahydronaphtalene)	0.02
14	Fluoranthene*	0.005	29	Benzo (c) phenanthrene	0.005
15	Dibenzo (a,h) anthracene*	0.005	30	Anthanthrene	0.005

* indicates a priority PAH molecule.

In total, 9 samples have been collected during two storm events on 07 and 17 Jan 2023: 3 samples have been analysed only for the dissolved fraction (D), and 6 for the total sample (T) (Table B12).

Table B12: List of collected samples with the analysed fraction (total sample or dissolved fraction).

Sampling time	Analysis fraction (D or T)*	CARSO reference nr.
07-Jan-2023 19:23	T	LSE2301-30329
07-Jan-2023 20:20	D	LSE2301-30328
07-Jan-2023 23:56	T	LSE2301-30327
17-Jan-2023 07:26	D	LSE2301-41136-1
17-Jan-2023 08:13	D	LSE2301-41137-1
17-Jan-2023 08:19	T	LSE2301-41138-1
17-Jan-2023 08:31	T	LSE2301-41140-1
17-Jan-2023 09:00	T	LSE2301-41139-1
17-Jan-2023 10:10	T	LSE2301-41141-1

* D: dissolved fraction sample, T: total sample

B.3.2. In situ data collection

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor has been installed in the flume of the Chassieu retention OTHU monitoring station (Figure B52 and Figure B53), from 30 May 2022 at 12:10 until 31 December 2022 at 23:58. Its data have been collected with a 2-min time step, like all other sensors in Chassieu. It was checked during the usual weekly maintenance visits. The data have been saved in a file named Chas1.csv, that contains the time, the rainfall intensity (mm/h), the monitoring flume feeding pump (pump on = 1; pump off = 0), the discharge and its standard uncertainty (both m³/s), the conductivity and its standard uncertainty (both µS/cm), the turbidity and its standard uncertainty (both NTU) and the Trios EnviroFlu-HC value (in µg/L). When the feeding pump is off, the monitoring flume contains only stagnant water and therefore conductivity, turbidity and PAH data are replaced by NaN (in a second file named Chas1NaN.csv as they are not representative of the stormwater (or dry weather peak flows) flowing in the catchment outlet sewer).

B.4. Results

B.4.1. Laboratory correlation

Measurements on the 9 samples are summarized in Table B13, Figure B55 and Figure B56. In Table B13, samples are grouped according to the analysed fraction: in grey for total sample, in blue for dissolved fraction. The mean sensor concentration C ($\mu\text{g/L}$), the standard deviation ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and the coefficient of variation CV (no unit) are calculated from the 240 measurements carried out for each sample with the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor. The last column gives the concentration of the sum of PAHs ($\mu\text{g/L}$) calculated as the sum of the concentrations of the 30 analysed PAHs molecules (values below LoQ have been set to zero for the sum calculation).

Table B13: Results of measurements on the 9 samples.

Sample	Fraction	Mean sensor C ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	std sensor C ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	CV (mean C/ std C)	Sum PAHs ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
07-Jan-2023 19:23:00	Total	64.32	5.20	0.08	0.129
07-Jan-2023 23:56:00	Total	84.03	5.31	0.06	0.135
17-Jan-2023 08:19:00	Total	48.55	5.03	0.10	0.720
17-Jan-2023 08:31:00	Total	26.85	5.06	0.19	0.741
17-Jan-2023 09:00:00	Total	27.48	5.24	0.19	0.303
17-Jan-2023 10:10:00	Total	14.64	7.06	0.48	0.287
07-Jan-2023 20:20:00	Dissolved	79.96	4.93	0.06	0.110
17-Jan-2023 07:26:00	Dissolved	49.96	4.54	0.09	0.012
17-Jan-2023 08:13:00	Dissolved	28.11	5.13	0.18	0.092

Figure B55 shows the boxplots of the 240 concentrations measured with the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor for each sample. For the rain event dated 07 Jan, concentrations range from 64 to 84 $\mu\text{g/L}$, and for the event dated 17 Jan from 15 to 50 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Concentrations in dissolved fractions are not significantly different from total concentrations. Standard deviations and coefficients of variation are large, with CV decreasing with concentration C , ranging from 48% for $C = 15 \mu\text{g/L}$ to about 6% for C around 80 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Figure B55: Boxplots of the 240 concentrations measured with the Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor for each sample (among the $9 \times 240 = 2160$ values, six were negative and have been replaced by NaN). Light blue columns indicate the three samples with analyses of dissolved fraction.

Figure B56 shows the bar plot of the CARSO laboratory measurements of PAHs concentrations. Only 18 among 30 PAH molecules have been quantified at least once in the 9 samples. Pyrene is the single molecule quantified in all samples, ranging from 0.012 to 0.175 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Fluoranthene and Benzo (b) fluoranthene are quantified in 7 and 6 samples respectively. Other molecules are quantified in 1 (Fluorene) to 5 samples only (Benzo (a) anthracene, Benzo (k) fluoranthene, Benzo (a) pyrene, Benzo (g,h,i) perylene, Chrysene, Benzo (j) fluoranthene, Benzo (e) pyrene and Anthanthrene). The laboratory concentrations are within the ranges usually reported in literature (e.g. Gasperi *et al.*, 2014; Becouze *et al.*, 2019) for urban stormwater.

Figure B56: Bar plot of CARSO laboratory measurements of PAHs concentrations. Only the 18 among 30 analysed PAHs that have been quantified (i.e. concentrations $> \text{LoQ}$) in at least one sample are displayed.

Figure B57 displays the sensor concentrations versus the laboratory concentrations. It appears immediately that sensor concentrations are 2 orders of magnitude larger than the laboratory concentrations and are much higher than PAHs concentrations reported in the literature. It seems that the sensor dramatically overestimates the PAHs concentrations.

Looking at the 6 grey points corresponding to measurements of total samples (T), one observes that the correlation is negative, which is not plausible ($r = -0.4239$). The regression line is

$$C_{\text{sensor}} = b_1 + b_2 C_{\text{lab}}$$

with $b_1 = 59.7745$, $b_2 = -40.3225$.

This regression is however extremely approximate as i) it is based only on 6 points, ii) the coefficients b_i are highly uncertainty with 95% confidence intervals respectively equal to [4.6068, 114.9421] and [-159.9265, 79.2814], and iii) an RMSE value equal to 26.6709 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

The 3 light blue points corresponding to measurements of dissolved fractions (D) do not show better results in terms of correlation with the sensor values. In addition, laboratory concentrations on dissolved fractions (D) are consistent, as they globally much lower than those measured on total samples (D), which corroborates the information in literature indicating that most PAHs are observed in the particulate fraction in stormwater runoff. This trend is not observed with the concentrations given by the sensor.

Figure B57: Plot of Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor concentrations vs. CARSO laboratory PAHs concentrations, with regression line for total sample concentrations.

From the above results, the sensor does not deliver representative and reliable results when it is used in stormwater.

B.4.2. In situ data collection

From 30 May 2022 12:10 to 31 December 2022 23:58, the feeding pump was 'on' during 321.7 h in total only, i.e. 6.2% of the time, mainly during storm events as expected. The data collected *in situ* during the periods the feeding pump was 'on' are displayed in Figure B58.

D6.2. Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems

Figure B58: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 30 May to 31 December 2022 with a 2-min time step. **a:** rainfall intensity, **b:** feeding pump, **c:** outlet discharge, **d:** conductivity, **e:** turbidity, **f:** PAH concentration.

During storm events, at first glance the PAH sensor concentration varies consistently with discharge and turbidity, despite frequent saturation of the PAH sensor (example of period 14 to 30 November 2022 in Figure B59). At the individual storm event scale (example of storm event dated 28-30 Nov. 2022 in Figure B60), the above statement is confirmed: when the sensor saturation and high peaks (visible on Figure B59d) are masked, the rest of the PAH sensor data (in the range 0-80 µg/L) and their evolution are to some extent similar to the turbidity data (Figure B60). This may be partly explained by the fact that the PAH sensor has no turbidity compensation and seems to be very strongly affected by this quantity. However, this is not confirmed by the absence of correlation between NTU and PAH sensor concentration: $r = 0.0257$ (see also Figure B61).

Figure B59: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume from 14 to 30 Nov 2022 with a 2-min time step. a: rainfall intensity, b: outlet discharge, c: turbidity, d: PAH concentration.

D6.2. Report on emerging monitoring technologies for urban drainage systems

Figure B60: Plots of the data collected in the Chassieu monitoring flume on 28-30 Nov 2022 with a 2-min time step. **a:** rainfall intensity, **b:** outlet discharge, **c:** turbidity, **d:** PAH concentration, **e:** zoom on PAH concentration under 80 µg/L.

Figure B61: PAH sensor concentration vs. turbidity on 28-30 November 2022.

A correlation analysis has shown that no correlation exists between PAH values on the one hand, and intensity, discharge, conductivity or turbidity on the other hand. Figure B58f, Figure B62 and Figure B63 show that i) PAH sensor concentration are highly variable, with several occurrences of saturation of the sensor at its maximum value of 500 µg/L, ii) the lack of correlation with outlet discharge and turbidity.

Figure B62: PAH sensor concentration vs. outlet discharge from 30 May to 31 December 2022.

Figure B63: PAH sensor concentration vs. turbidity from 30 May to 31 December 2022.

In addition, the order of magnitude of the PAH concentration, as shown in laboratory correlation, are unrealistic for PAHs concentrations in stormwater. As reported in literature, a possible explanation is that the PAH sensor may be affected by interference from other molecules, e.g. like humic acids, also present in stormwater, which are contributing to fluorescence (e.g. Bressy *et al.*, 2014). Any molecule with a structure similar to PAH molecules structures may generate a response in fluorescence: in other words, it is difficult, in a water matrix containing a great diversity of organic molecules, to have a selective PAH probe (Wiest, 2023). Maybe a more sophisticated raw data processing method (like e.g. Excitation Emission Matrix) would be necessary to improve the quantification of mixtures of PAH in stormwater (Bressy *et al.*, 2014; Bonhomme and Bressy, 2016; Yang *et al.*, 2019).

From a practical point of view, the PAH sensor was easy to maintain and cleanse periodically, despite its rather heavy weight requiring a strong support device. No specific maintenance problem has been reported during the testing period from 30 May to 31 December 2022.

B.5. Conclusion

The Trios EnviroFlu-HC sensor does not seem to be reliably used directly for online measurements of PAH concentration in stormwater due to

- lack of correlation and large difference in order of magnitude between sensor data and PAH laboratory analyses in the same samples;
- difficulty to relate *in situ* measurements with diverse PAH molecules due to possible interferences with other molecules in stormwater and the fact that PAHs in stormwater are mainly observed in the particulate phase.

B.6. Data sets

All data are available in the following files:

- For laboratory calibration: PAHs.csv
- For *in situ* data collection: Chas1zero.csv and Chas1NaN.csv

Appendix References

- Becouze-Lareure, C., Dembélé, A., Coquery, M., Cren-Olivé, C., Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L. (2019). Assessment of 34 dissolved and particulate organic and metallic micropollutants discharged at the outlet of two contrasted urban catchments. *Science of the Total Environment*, 651, 1810-1818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.042>.
- Bonhomme, C., Bressy, A. (2016). La mesure en continu des HAP par fluorescence. Séminaire thématique OPUR, Micropolluants : devenir et méthodes innovantes de suivi, 22 juin 2016, Paris France. (in French).
- Bressy, A., Boutin G., Bonhomme, C. (2014). How to continuously monitor PAHs in urban stormwater using in situ UV-fluorescence technology? 13th International Conference on Urban Drainage, Sarawak, Malaysia; 7-12 Sep. 2014, 7.
- Gasperi, J., Sebastian, C., Ruban, V. et al. (2014). Micropollutants in urban stormwater: occurrence, concentrations, and atmospheric contributions for a wide range of contaminants in three French catchments. *Environ Sci Pollut Res.*, 21, 5267–5281. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-013-2396-0>
- Keith, L. H. (2014). The Source of U.S. EPA’s Sixteen PAH Priority Pollutants. *Polycyclic Aromatic Compounds*, 35(2–4), 147–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10406638.2014.892886>
- Wenzl, T., Simon, R., Anklam, E., Kleiner, J. (2006). Analytical methods for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in food and the environment needed for new food legislation in the European Union. *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 25(7), 716-725. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2006.05.010>.
- Wiest L. (2023). Personal communication.
- Yang, Y.Z., Peleato, N.M., Legge, R.L., Andrews, R.C. (2019). Fluorescence excitation emission matrices for rapid detection of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and pesticides in surface waters. *Environ. Sci.: Water Res. Technol.*, 5, 315-324. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8EW00821C>

Appendix C: Assessment of DischargeKeeper Flow Monitoring Quality

Jörg Rieckermann (Eawag)

C.0. Executive Summary

This assessment compares the flow measurements of the DischargeKeeper system against high-quality reference data from a Nivus ultrasonic flow meter installed at the HALL infrastructure at Eawag, with the aim of evaluating the accuracy and robustness of the DischargeKeeper technology under typical sewer operating conditions. The analysis visual reference data inspection through scattergraphs, analysis of residual flows, and a categorization of deviations over different flow regimes and over time. The data comparison was conducted on 1-minute averaged flow measurements, with a focus on the time period of April 2019. Using fitted Manning curves, a $\pm 20\%$ threshold was applied to identify hydraulically credible Nivus measurements based on their alignment with theoretical depth-velocity behaviour. This allowed for a fair and reliable comparison with DischargeKeeper data.

Residual statistics show that DischargeKeeper consistently underestimates flow, with accuracy improving at higher flow levels. The mean bias decreases from -15.6 l/s (-21.4%) at low flows to -8.0 l/s (-6.8%) at high flows, and RMSE drops from 18.0 l/s to 11.6 l/s, indicating more reliable performance under higher flow conditions. Although the accuracy of the NIVUS flow meter is not supposed to be comparable to laboratory conditions, and it has not been validated with independent flow tracer measurements, the comparison suggest that the DischargeKeeper performs well at medium and high flows, while low flows show larger biases—likely due to velocity profile assumptions and sensor sensitivity. A scatterplot confirms this, with strong agreement at high flows and underestimation at low flows, which could possibly be caused by a lower resolutions, or less accurate assumptions in transforming surface velocities into flows, e.g. transient hydraulics and different operational roughness for different flow conditions.

C.1. Objective

This report assesses the accuracy and reliability of the DischargeKeeper flow monitoring system based on comparison with Nivus reference measurements. The DischargeKeeper is a camera-based system that predicts flows from surface velocity measurements. For the JRA on Smart Sensing (WP6), it has been improved by deriving flow from surface velocities by means of computational Fluid Dynamics simulations.

Using methods described in literature and scattergraph analysis, the performance of DischargeKeeper is evaluated under varying hydraulic conditions. Unfortunately, the data used for comparison only cover the period from 2019-4-19 00:00 - 2019-4-19 23:59.

C.2. Material

This analysis is based on flow measurements from two independent sensors: the DischargeKeeper (a non-contact image-based flow monitoring system) and a Nivus ultrasonic flow meter installed in a full-scale urban sewer system (Figure B64). The evaluation focuses on a single 24-hour period, April 16, 2019, during which both instruments were operating concurrently.

While the Nivus sensor is commonly used as a reference system, its data are not inherently error-free. Therefore, to ensure a reliable baseline for comparison, we applied scattergraph analysis techniques to identify and retain only the hydraulically credible measurements. The resulting subset of Nivus data serves as the reference dataset against which the DischargeKeeper performance is assessed. The Nivus dataset included:

- Timestamped flow rate [l/s]
- Flow depth [m]
- Flow velocity [m/s]

Figure B64: Flow data at experimental Hall of Eawag. NIVUS OCM-Pro, 2019-04-01 until 2019-05-31. Yellow range labels data used in comparison (2019-04-16), Grey Area depicts typical dry weather conditions used for Scattergraph reference.

C.3. Methods

Overview

The performance evaluation of the DischargeKeeper was carried out in several steps, including data filtering, scattergraph analysis, residual calculation, and performance benchmarking. All time series were resampled to 1-minute averages to harmonize temporal resolution and reduce sensor noise.

Data Preprocessing

- Date of Analysis: April 16, 2019
- Reference Data: Nivus ultrasonic flow measurements
- Resampling: Both Nivus and DischargeKeeper data were downsampled to 1-minute intervals.
- Residual Calculation: Flow residuals were computed as

$$\text{Residual Flow} = \text{DischargeKeeper} - \text{Nivus}$$

Credible Flow Filtering via Scattergraph Analysis

To filter out questionable Nivus data, we implemented a scattergraph-based credibility check, which plots flow depth vs. velocity and compares observed patterns against a theoretical Manning-Gauckler-Strickler curve (Enfinger & Stevens, 2008; Curry, 2006). The procedure is:

1. A Manning curve was fitted using dry weather flow data from April 22–25, assumed to represent stable, subcritical conditions without hydraulic anomalies.
2. For each data point on April 16, the expected velocity was calculated based on the fitted curve using the observed flow depth.
3. A data point was classified as credible if the observed velocity was within $\pm 20\%$ of the predicted Manning velocity at the same depth.

This technique is grounded in established hydrodynamic analysis practices (Enfinger & Stevens, 2008). It helps distinguish valid measurements from artifacts due to:

- Transitional flows (e.g., bores or hydraulic jumps)
- Backwater effects
- Sensor drift or blockage

By applying this physically based filtering method, we derived a subset of Nivus data that aligns closely with hydraulic expectations, improving the confidence in residual analysis and performance benchmarking.

Flow Categorization for Performance Evaluation

To assess performance under different hydraulic conditions, the Nivus flows were stratified into three quantile-based categories [<94.6 ; $94.6 - 109.3$; >109.3] (Table B5). These categories enable analysis of the DischargeKeeper's performance under varying flow regimes, from dry weather baseflow to elevated wet weather conditions.

Performance Indicators

For each flow category, the following key performance indicators (KPIs) were computed to provide insight into the sensor's bias, variability, and overall accuracy across hydraulic regimes (Table B5):

- Mean Bias (absolute and relative)
- Standard Deviation
- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) (absolute and relative)

C.4. Results

Selecting Credible Nivus Data by Scattergraph Analysis

The full Nivus flow time series (April–May 2019) reveals a number of irregular patterns and data quality issues. While typical dry weather patterns can be observed (Figure B64, Figure B65) — particularly around late April—the dataset also includes frequent zero-flow values, which are not hydraulically credible in a combined sewer context. These flatlined or null readings likely indicate temporary signal loss, sensor malfunction, or post-processing errors.

The periods of missing or flatlined data compromise the reliability of the full dataset for continuous flow analysis, particularly for wet weather response and daily flow pattern validation. Additionally, short-duration spikes and erratic drops suggest noise or outliers that were not fully filtered. These issues underscore the importance of validating Nivus data with additional sources (e.g. velocity-depth consistency, secondary sensors) and using scattergraph-based filtering, to isolate hydraulically plausible data.

Figure B65: Left: typical dry weather conditions used for scattergraph analysis, Right: Scattergraph resulted in regular flow behaviour with an estimated roughness of $n=0.0174$.

Figure B66: Top, left: Scattergraph of the Nivus data, right: Credible data within $\pm 20\%$ of the Manning-relationship. Bottom: Left: Discharge keeper compared to credible NIVUS data (1min aggregation), Discharge keeper compared to credible NIVUS data (5min aggregation)

Scattergraph Analysis

The resulting set of credible points shows tight adherence to the fitted Manning curve, as seen in Figure B65 (right). After filtering the Nivus dataset with the Manning model, a hydraulically credible subset of flow measurements was obtained. These data were used as a reference to evaluate the accuracy and precision of the DischargeKeeper system under varying flow conditions.

Overall Performance

Across the full dataset, the DischargeKeeper consistently underestimated flow compared to the Nivus reference (). The overall mean bias was -11.1 l/s, corresponding to a relative bias of -12.6% . The root mean square error (RMSE) was 14.1 l/s, or 16.9% in relative terms. This indicates moderate disagreement between the two sensors, particularly at lower flows.

Figure B67: Scatterplot of credible NIVUS vs. DK data shows that the DK underestimates the flow data, but deviations are not large in medium and high flows.

Performance by Flow Category

To assess how sensor agreement varies with hydraulic regime, the data were divided into three quantile-based categories based on Nivus flow values (Table XX). These results clearly show that DischargeKeeper’s accuracy improves with increasing flow. The mean bias reduces from -15.6 l/s at low flows to -8.0 l/s at high flows. Similarly, the RMSE drops from 18.0 l/s to 11.6 l/s, and the relative error more than halves—from nearly 25% in low flow to under 10% in high flow.

Table B14: Summary of DischargeKeeper performance across Nivus-defined flow categories. The accuracy improves with increasing flow, as shown by decreasing bias and RMSE values from low to high flow conditions.

Flow category	Flow range	Mean Bias		RMSE	
		[l/s]	[%]	[l/s]	[%]
Low	≤ 94.6	-15.6	-21.4	18.0	24.9
Medium	94.6–109.3	-9.7	-9.5	11.9	11.7
High	> 109.3	-8.0	-6.8	11.6	9.8
<i>Overall</i>		<i>-11.1</i>	<i>-12.6</i>	<i>14.1</i>	<i>16.9</i>

Residual Distribution

The distribution of residuals (DischargeKeeper – Nivus) is skewed toward underestimation, particularly at lower flows. Boxplots and time-series visualizations of residuals (see Figure 5) show tighter agreement under high-flow conditions and larger, more variable discrepancies during baseflow periods.

Temporal Pattern of Residuals

The residuals vary throughout the day, with the most significant discrepancies during early morning hours—likely due to unstable or transitional hydraulic conditions.

Figure B68: Comparison of DischargeKeeper and Nivus flow measurements for April 16, 2019. Top: Time series of 1-minute averaged flow rates from the DischargeKeeper and the credible Nivus meter, filtered with a low-pass parameter $n=0.0174$, Bottom Left: Boxplot of residual flow (DischargeKeeper minus Nivus) stratified by Nivus flow clusters (Low, Medium, High), showing a decrease in bias and variability with increasing flow, Bottom Right: Residuals over time, color-coded by flow cluster, highlighting larger discrepancies during low-flow conditions and improved agreement at higher flows.

C.5. Conclusions

The DischargeKeeper shows reliable performance in medium and high flow regimes, demonstrating good agreement with a reference ultrasonic flow meter (NIVUS OCMPro). However, its accuracy diminishes during low-flow conditions, which is consistent with known challenges in transitional or unstable hydraulic regimes, where flow behavior deviates from ideal open-channel conditions. To improve reliability, we suggest:

- investigate low-flow deviations using CFD analysis, particularly to assess the impact of biofilm on wall roughness and effective hydraulic radius. These factors may increase friction losses and affect velocity estimates (Huisman, 2001).
- prioritize deployment in locations with steady, subcritical flow to minimize the influence of hydraulic transitions.
- incorporate regular scattergraph reviews to identify and interpret transitional flow signatures, sensor drift, or hydraulic anomalies.
- supplement low-flow data with additional measurements or apply quality flags, enabling more robust interpretation and filtering of uncertain readings.

C.5. References:

- Curry, B. (2006). Recognizing Scattergraph Patterns: Flow Monitoring Diagnostics. ADS Environmental Services. Presented at: Water Environment Federation (WEF) Collection Systems Specialty Conference.
- Enfinger, K., & Stevens, M. (2008) Recognizing the Scattergraph Signature of an SSO (Sanitary Sewer Overflow). ADS Environmental Services.
- Huisman, J. L. (2001). Transport and Transformation Processes in Combined Sewers (Doctoral dissertation, ETH Zurich, No. 13989). <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-a-004202356>